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Integration and Determinants of Psychosocial Health

Thematic Report

Önver Cetrez, Fairuzah Atchulo,

Ingrid Garosi, Annika Hack,

Md Arifuzzaman Rajon

Uppsala University

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Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to us at: cetrez@teol.uu.se

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List of abbreviations

AU	Austria
DE	Germany
EU	European Union
GR	Greece
IGOs	Intergovernmental Organisations
IR	Iraq
NGOs	Non Governmental Organisations
PO	Poland
SWE	Sweden
TR	Turkey
UK	United Kingdom
UN	United Nations
UNHCR	United Nations High Commission for Refugees
WHO	World Health Organisation

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About the project

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project which aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of 14 partners from 11 source, transit and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden. The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-national comparative research and to critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and third countries.

RESPOND will study migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanisation. Each thematic field reflects a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and is designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impacts and the responses given by affected actors within.

In order to better focus on these themes, we divided our research question into work packages (WPs). The present thematic report is concerned with the findings related to WP5, which focuses specifically on psychosocial health among newcomers.

Executive summary

This report analyses an important aspect of migrant life: psychosocial health among migrant newcomers. To this respect, it draws data and findings from the RESPOND reports in several work packages. This report employs a methodology of transdisciplinary research design, by establishing a strong collaboration beyond discipline-specific approaches, exchanging information and sharing sources. While the general analysis in RESPOND is structured along macro (policy), meso (implementation) and micro (individual) levels, this report focuses primarily on newcomers' experiences at the micro level.

The report aims at exposing the distinct relation between newcomers' psychosocial health and their new environment. In this regard, it is aimed at showing that the environment's resources and opportunities as well as their attributed meanings play a key role in the processes of adaptation, coping and building resilience. (Forced) migration and resettlement, often accompanied by horrendous experiences in their country of origin, inhuman conditions on their migratory journey (including border management) and consumptive encounters with the host society and administrative personnel, often lead to strains on one's life conditions and can have an impact on newcomers' health, both physically and mentally. Therefore, this report aims at exemplifying in which way psychosocial determinants can affect a person's resilience, outlook on life and their integration into the host society.

The determination of the psychosocial health of newcomers is made through elaborations of the various factors (internal or external) that positively or negatively affect health. This report also highlights the ways that newcomers navigate settling in and integrating into new surroundings, and the various ways they shore up resilience and which coping methods are used. The report further provides analyses on whether gender and country of origin bear an impact on the health and resilience of newcomers via quantitative' data analysing newcomers' vulnerability.

The report is structured in seven sections. The first section provides an overview of the conceptual framework instrumental to analysing and understanding data, specifically focusing on the Social-Ecological Model of Resilience, the ADAPT Model, and Coping. These explain and provide context to categorising the various factors - internal or/and external - and the ways they positively/negatively shape the health of newcomers, and the avenues availed for finding coping methods and resilience. Moreover, this section also includes other concepts such as culture, acculturation and discrimination, that influence the path of newcomers towards health and resilience.

The other sections provide the analyses of newcomers' experiences with respect to their psycho-social health. This is done through a compilation and analysis of the various experiences of newcomers across various countries within the RESPOND project. Analyses also include a thematic overview of newcomers' vulnerabilities based on gender and country of origin, and finally an analysis of newcomers' experience of health based on the Social-ecological Model of Resilience and the ADAPT Model. This further includes an analysis of the newcomers' responses regarding adaptive and extreme responses. The conclusions drawn from this report on "Integration and Determinants of Psychosocial Health" are followed by specific policy recommendations.

Based on this analysis, this report finds the following:

- Psychosocial determinants such as legal status, arrest and/or detention at the borders, exposure to violence, etc. have a negative impact on newcomers' health.

- Almost all countries had problematic factors such as asylum rejections, border arrests and exposure to trauma, etc. which negatively affected newcomers' health.
- Where possible, the ability to choose housing helps newcomers in settling down into their new homes and it supports resilience mechanisms.
- Distinct discrimination in accessing the labour market and the resultant lack of income negatively impact health.
- Most newcomers suffer from physical and psychological ill-health. In the UK, an increase in cases of depression, PTSD, attempted suicide and self-harm; in Poland, stress related to previous and present trauma were experienced as in Austria and Turkey. In the UK and Austria, stress was also connected to lengthy asylum procedures. In particular in Turkey, stress was also seen as causing somatic ill-health. In Iraq, some health-related issues were manifested after inhuman or degrading treatment in reception facilities.
- Religion and spirituality are prevalent coping mechanisms, with variations of positive and negative outcomes.
- Gender is a significant marker of vulnerability: women are more vulnerable due to pregnancies and making the migratory journey accompanied by a minor, and a risk of experiencing more sexual and psychological abuse and/or rape.
- Newcomers' country of origin is a marker of vulnerability: Afghan newcomers are more vulnerable to negative experiences than Syrians and Iraqis.
- Adaptive responses are shown among newcomers with access to resources (such as healthcare, housing, psychological support) while maladaptive responses are shown among newcomers with limited or no access to resources (healthcare, income, support)

1. Introduction

The 2015 refugee emergency is one of the biggest challenges that the European Union (EU) has faced since its establishment. This report will outline a multi-level framework of determinants of mental health for newcomers in a resettlement situation. While the public health field, as Mawani points out, largely approaches research from a deficit perspective that emphasises risk factors for illness (Mawani, 2014, in Simich & Andermann, 2014), the approach here is based both on risk factors and protective factors that prevent negative health outcomes and/or promote health. In order to understand the risk factors, the discrepancies in mental health factors for refugees is important. It is also important to scrutinise the complex intersecting dimensions in their lives. The public health and policy analyst, F. Mawani, points out that disparities in mental health outcomes among refugees are attributable to inequalities in social determinants, including macro-, community-, family-, and individual levels (Mawani, 2014, in Simich & Andermann, 2014). To understand the protective factors, we start with the ontology of humanistic and existential psychology that human beings are capable of reflexivity and self-change and have the capacity or reservoir of potential. This was pointed out already at the end of the 19th century, by the early psychologist William James' concept of *strenuousness*, as an activity to resist ill-health (Simich & Andermann, 2014). As researchers we are learning that the traumatic effects of war do not necessarily doom people to life-long suffering (Simich & Andermann, 2014), but rather that different determinants restore refugee health, of which personal strength and culture are important components.

Integration can conceptually be defined in many ways, which adds to the complexity and richness of the topic, necessitating an interdisciplinary approach to comprehend its broader consequences at individual and societal levels. A heuristic model for the empirical study of integration was developed by Penninx and Garcés-Mascareñas (2016), where they identify three analytically distinct dimensions in the definition of integration: legal/political, socio-economic and cultural/religious, all three on individual, collective/group and institutional levels, relevant for the immigrant population as well as the receiving society. These dimensions are not independent, but related in an interactive mode. The focus of this report is mainly on the immigrant population, in interaction with the meso level of stakeholders. While earlier reports in the project (WP1, WP5) have mainly highlighted and presented the legal/political dimension (macro level), in this report we present material primarily related to the individual and collective/group levels among newcomers, in terms of health concerns. These are also linked to family, significant others, collective group, religious or other worldview, and interaction with stakeholders, as well as stakeholders' experiences when relevant.

The term integration is itself complex. While some studies highlight the process that immigrants undergo after their arrival in the destination country, other studies point to the determinants of migration (thus before arrival). However, as Castles and Miller (2009) point out, research should engage with the migratory process as a whole. When approaching integration as increasing social membership in the destination country (Bartram, Poros & Monforte 2014), one can, in an analytical sense, distinguish integration (developing competency in two or more cultures) as one strategy among other strategies: assimilation (developing competency in the new culture and giving up the old one), separation (maintaining the old culture, without adhering to the new one), and marginalisation (not having competency in any of the relevant cultures); a process of what is termed

acculturation; more on acculturation in the next section, Conceptual framework (see Rudmin, 2009; Berry, 2006).

1.1. Method, Material and Sources

The RESPOND project as well as this thematic report have largely applied a transdisciplinary research design, by establishing a strong collaboration beyond discipline-specific approaches (psychology of religion, cultural psychology, geography, political science, ethnography, sociology), exchanging information and sharing sources. While the overall level of analysis in RESPOND is structured along macro (policy), meso (implementation) and micro (individual) levels, this report focuses primarily on the micro level (for the other levels, see the different WP5 country reports within the RESPOND project). Data utilised for this report consists of interview data from the country reports within RESPOND as well as quantitized data, available as open access in the RESPOND database (Cetrez & Barthoma, 2020). The term *quantitizing*, as coined by Tashakkori and Teddlie (1998), is explained by Sandelowski (2000):

Quantitizing refers to a process by which qualitative data are treated with quantitative techniques to transform them into quantitative data. The researcher must first reduce verbal or visual data (e.g. from interviews, observations, artefacts, or documents) into items, constructs, or variables that are intended to mean only one thing and that can, therefore, be represented numerically. One of the most commonly used examples of this process is the creation of items for an instrument from interview data (p. 253).

The empirical material for this report is based on the RESPOND-project (www.respondmigration.com). The focus of this report is the migrants themselves, a micro-perspective, using interview material based on semi-structured interviews, designed within the RESPOND project. The interviews were made during 2019-2020. The themes covered in these interviews were several, structured along the project in large, but the themes used for this report are mainly linked to migrants' health concerns in the destination countries.

The overall RESPOND material consists of interviews from ten countries: Sweden (n=71), Germany (n=77), Italy (n=29), Greece (n=42), Austria (n=29), Poland (n=30), the UK (n=15), Hungary (n=20), Turkey (n=103), and Iraq (n=58), in total 474.¹ The majority of participants were from Syria (n=292), Afghanistan (n=56), and Iraq (n=59), but also from other countries, such as Iran, Russia, Nigeria, Pakistan, Turkey, Cameroon, Gambia (n=127), more than half were men (58.6%), almost two thirds (56.7%) in age group 27-50 years, followed by one third (29%) in age group 18-26, and one tenth (10.7%) in age group 51+. The majority of participants had a higher secondary or tertiary (e.g. university degree) education (42.3%), followed by lower secondary (17%), elementary school (9.4%), and illiterate (6,2%). Furthermore, the majority were married (54%) or single (30%), with smaller numbers who were divorced, engaged or widowed.

The empirical material is analysed through a procedure of qualitative content analysis, using NVivo. Through a deductive approach, we have used conceptual themes to structure this report and define the content of each category in terms of inclusion and exclusion. Along with this, we have used an inductive approach when choosing the codes that best reflect the

¹ Interview numbers differed in each country based on partners involved in the project and their ability to conduct fieldwork.

conceptual themes, as well as kept an openness towards material not covered by our framework.

As for the project in general, we have received ethics clearance from the relevant authorities in the respective countries. Thus, for more detailed sampling and material description in each country report, we refer to the respective reports found on the RESPOND web page, Working Paper Series (<https://respondmigration.com/wp-blog>).

2. Conceptual Framework

The use of operational definitions allows a move from general ideas and constructs to more specific measurable events or entities. Thus, in the following, the central concepts will be defined, among these culture, acculturation, discrimination, resilience, coping and meaning.

2.1. Culture and Acculturation

2.1.1. Culture

Culture refers to internal, external, behavioural as well as mental dimensions. A useful definition of culture is presented by the cultural psychologist Marsella (2005):

Culture is shared learned behavior and meanings that are socially transferred in various life-activity settings for purposes of individual and collective adjustment and adaptation. Cultures can be (1) transitory (i.e. situational even for a few minutes), (2) enduring (e.g., ethnocultural life styles), and in all instances are (3) dynamic (i.e., constantly subject to change and modification. Cultures are represented (4) internally (i.e., values, beliefs, attitudes, axioms, orientations, epistemologies, consciousness levels, perceptions, expectations, personhood) and (5) externally (i.e., artifacts, roles, institutions, social structures). Cultures (6) shape and construct our realities (i.e., they contribute to our world views, perceptions, orientations) and with this, our concepts of normality/abnormality, morality, aesthetics, and a number of arbiters of life. (p. 657)

Thus, when we use culture in this report, we refer to those practices that take place between individuals (interpersonal) as well as to meso level institutions, for example health care, and macro level norms and systems, for example norms about what are healthy or unhealthy practices.

2.1.2. Acculturation

Acculturation refers to the phenomena occurring when individuals from different cultures come into first hand contact (Pedersen, Fukuyama & Heath, 1989). Literally, acculturation has been described as moving towards a culture. This definition specifies acculturation as a change occurring not only within one group, i.e., the minority, but also within all the cultures involved in the encounter. Yet, in practice more change occurs in the nondominant group than in the dominant one (Organista, 1998), depending on power relationships (DeMarinis, Grzymala-Moszczyńska & Jablonski, 2002). To the above definition it is also important to add what Oppedal, Røysamb, and Sam (2004) point out, that acculturation is a “developmental process towards adaptation and gaining competence within more than one cultural setting” (p. 482).

Integration

Integration in the economic and political sphere would mean that immigrants participate in the labour market and enjoy political rights on equal terms with natives. In the social identity and belonging sphere it would mean to feel that one in some meaningful sense could identify with the host country or gain citizenship. However, aside from the personal ability of immigrants, such as gaining language skills or cultural competency, what is at stake here is

also the level of inclusion and exclusion of newcomers in different societies, due to normatively laden expectations of integration. Thus, acculturation includes coping with social and psychological conflicts (intrapsychic or interpersonal), for example, when cultural norms clash, or when gender roles and relationships are renegotiated and women take novel positions of power in their family (Suárez-Orozco, 2000; Nelson et al., 2016). Rudmin (2009) documented two critical social determinants of acculturation: the migrant's socioeconomic situation and their perception of discrimination in society.

An important field of acculturation research relates education and language skills to measures of health, for example, experienced stress and depression (Wrobel, Farrag & Hymes, 2009; Hahn & Truman, 2015). Van Tubergen (2010) elucidated the links between post-migration language acquisition and pre-migration factors such as schooling, age at the time of migration, geographic mobility, time spent in refugee reception facilities, completion of integration courses and other education, intention to remain in the host country, and complex health problems. Other research has demonstrated that negative health outcomes are linked to refugee- or temporary resident status (Steel et al., 2006), pre-migration traumatic events and continuous high levels of stress (Rian & Hodge, 2010), psychopathology, and postmigration living problems (Laban et al., 2005), abuse (Padela & Heisler, 2010), and experiences of discrimination, detention, dispersal, destitution, delayed decisions on asylum, denial of the right to work, or denial to healthcare – the seven D's (McKenzie, Tuck, & Agic, 2014). A systematic literature review by Bogic et al. (2015) showed that higher exposure to traumatic experiences and post-migration stress were the most common factors consistently associated with higher rates of mental disorders in war-refugees.

Studies on identity and acculturation (Cetrez, 2005, 2011, 2015) cautions against a simplistic understanding of belonging as an either-or identification with a given culture. Allegiance to multiple groups is promoted by what Collie, Kindon, and Posiadlowski (2010) describe as a mindful, strategic, and contextual identity negotiation, as is the coexistence within one person of different ethnic identities (Sirina et al., 2008).

2.2. Discrimination

In this report, we pay specific attention to discrimination. A definition of the term is: "a socially structured and sanctioned phenomenon, justified by ideology and expressed in interactions, among and between individuals and institutions, intended to maintain privileges for members of dominant groups at the cost of deprivation of others" (Krieger, 2000, in Simich & Andermann, 2014, 44). To this we may add the level of subjective feeling; i.e., perceived discrimination. Refugees may experience systematic discrimination, referring to "the totality of ways in which societies foster discrimination," institutional discrimination, being "discriminatory policies or practices carried out by state or nonstate institutions," and interpersonal discrimination, referring to "directly perceived discriminatory interactions between individuals" (Krieger, 2000, in Simich & Andermann, 2014, 44-45). Discrimination affects mental health directly or indirectly, by limiting access to health care and social services as well as to education and employment (Simich & Andermann, 2014). It can also traumatise, re-traumatise and disempower people, specifically those who have been persecuted in their country of origin.

2.3. Migration, Resettlement and Mental Health

With regard to the specific context of flight and migration, it becomes clear that people seeking refuge away from their home country have had to face great adversity. The process of adapting to the circumstances in their new environment is influenced by experiences of hardship they escaped from as “pre-migration adversities (...) [which] may affect their [refugee applicants] health.” (McKenzie et al., 2014, 184). The privation they have had to endure during the transit period and the struggles and discrimination accompanying resettlement can additionally impact newcomer’s psychological health in a negative way (McKenzie et al. 2014, 184). Therefore, distress can derive from or be intensified by post-migration worries about, for example, employment because “taking meaningful work and choice away from people renders them helpless” (Kirmayer, 2014, viii), in Simich & Andermann, 2014). In this sense, the denial of the right to work is included in the seven D’s, introduced by McKenzie et al. (2014), which are “[t]he factors that have an impact on [the] psychological health of asylum-seekers” (McKenzie et al. 2014, 184). Another determinant of mental health refers to the uncertainty of legal status during the resettlement period, in the sense that “long delays in deciding outcomes are corrosive to well-being and confidence” (Kirmayer, 2014, viii, cf. McKenzie et al., 2014, 184). Consequently, “it is increasingly accepted that post-migration adversities, including aspects of the asylum system, social isolation, poverty and cultural alienation can compound the impacts of the pre-migration and migration process.” (McKenzie et al., 2014, 184). Another determinant of mental health concerns the well-being of family and friends, in the sense “that ensuring the safety of loved ones left behind and reuniting with one’s family” (Kirmayer, 2014, viii).

Although the insecurity about what the future holds in store for newcomers is a constant stressor and aggravates their suffering, it is important to denote that they develop personal strategies which enhance their resilience. Thus, protective mechanisms countering risk factors are made use of and influence personal development. Resilience and individual trajectory, however, depend on psychosocial determinants as well as on the resources which are available in the new (as in any) environment. Among these are very prominently the reliance on interpersonal networks by e.g. finding joy, hope and purpose in their children by focusing on their future (Cetrez et al., 2020, 66-67). Furthermore, the exploration of ethnicity and spirituality have been mentioned as sources of relief and of conveying feelings of security and stability (Cetrez et al., 2020, 66). Connected to this is the maintenance of cultural identity by for example making use of one’s native language and adhering to religious-cultural practices familiar to the newcomers.

In the following, the social-ecology framework for resilience which analyses the interaction of the different systems in which the individual is embedded will be presented. The framework was developed after Tol et al. in Panter-Brick and Eggerman (2012), Ungar (2012) and Simich and Andermann (2014). It is preceded by a brief introduction to the concepts of resilience and coping, including positive and negative religious coping.

2.3.1. Resilience

Resilience as a term used in the psychological sciences, started to appear frequently in the 1980s and was synonymously used “for the ability of individuals to recover from exposure to chronic and acute stress” (Ungar, 2012, 13). It was further developed that resilience is the coping behaviour of individuals in the face of great adversity, thus “[r]esilience refers to a class of phenomena characterised by *good outcomes in spite of serious threats to*

adaptation or development.” (Masten 2001, 228, emphasis in original). Hence, the individual is required to muster great hardiness, durability and adaptation in order to master episodes of peril and sorrow and to avoid succumbing to misery. In this sense, “resilience is part of what has helped humans survive” (Pickren, 2014, 18). Taking into consideration this definition, the study of resilience conversely focuses on “*what* helps them [humans] to move on and regain stability and productivity” (Simich, 2014, 3, emphasis added).

For a way to operationalise resilience as an adaptive response, we can look at the three processes of recovery, sustainability, and growth, as presented in this figure by Murray and Zautra (in Ungar, 2012, 338), with some modifications for refugee situations.

Figure 1. Resilience trajectories of recovery, sustainability and growth

Source: Murray and Zautra, in Ungar, 2012, 338

In order to investigate what makes for the capacity to cope with situations of great risk, early studies on human development focused predominantly on personal characteristics such as the individual’s abilities, strengths, motivation, traits and talents as well as genetic predispositions as factors influencing the individual’s personal adaptation skills. In 1979 Urie Bronfenbrenner already criticised this one-dimensional approach and highlighted the shortcomings in acknowledging the profound importance of the environment’s influence on the individual by asserting that “[w]hat we find in practice (...) is a marked asymmetry, a hypertrophy of theory and research focusing on the properties of the person and only the most rudimentary conception and characterization of the environment in which the person is found.” (Bronfenbrenner, 1979, 16).

Accordingly, earlier psychological studies of human behaviour and development focused more thoroughly on the person than on the environment, let alone the interaction between the two (Bronfenbrenner, 1979, 16). Although extra-individual factors were accounted for, they were not made the focus of the research because “personal qualities” were regarded “as the *sine quo non* of developmental outcomes” (Ungar, 2012, 15, emphasis in original) of

this individualistic approach. As opposed to this, further studies of resilience established conceptualisations of this phenomenon by looking more in-depth at structural factors and by focusing on “how the fabric of a society impacts individual mental health trajectories.” (Panter-Brick, Eggerman, 2012, 369). This is also accounted for in the presumptions of the Adaptation and Development after Persecution and Trauma (ADAPT) model after Silove (2013) which will be presented below. The model asserts that “[t]he social world mirrors and interacts with the personal/psychic world, creating a process of recursive, or looped, feedback.” (Silove, 2013, 238). As a consequence, this perspective does not regard the individual and their environment (eco/social context) as independent entities but rather emphasises the interaction between them, which is their reciprocal relationship (Panter-Brick, Eggerman, 2012, 369).

2.3.2. Cultural Dimension

Criticism of earlier resilience research points out the overemphasis on the individualised nature of adaptation, typical of mainstream populations, and the lack of sensitivity to community and cultural factors in contextualising resilience practices (Ungar, 2008; Bottrell, 2009). Or, as Summerfield (1996) highlighting the cultural differences in resilience concepts:

The cultural emphasis [among non-Western people] is on dependency and interdependency rather than the autonomy and individualisation on which many western ideas about mental injury are predicated.

The many dimensions of culture in health research are complex. However, culture influences our perceptions of and beliefs about health and illness (Kleinman, 1980; Simich & Andermann, 2014). Also, as cultures are both dynamic and static for some period of time (Marsella, 2005), the inherent beliefs, values, and practices of a cultural group may either change and develop, or get preserved when people find themselves faced with the risk of losing them (Simich & Andermann, 2014).

Our knowledge of processes of resilience among non-western cultures is limited, pointing at a need for additional cross-cultural research and theory development in resilience processes (Ungar, 2012). Thus, a culturally and contextually sensitive definition of resilience presented by Ungar (2008, 225), indicating both the process of navigation and negotiation, is preferable:

In the context of exposure to significant adversity, whether psychological, environmental, or both, resilience is both the capacity of individuals to navigate their way to health-sustaining resources, including opportunities to experience feelings of well-being, and a condition of the individual’s family, community and culture to provide these health resources and experiences in culturally meaningful ways.

Ungar’s constructivist approach emphasises the significance of social relations, thus challenging dominant discourse of pathology and health, arguing that judgments about normalcy, deviance and health held by researchers may be opposite to those held by participants, or as he writes: “[f]or many children, patterns of deviance are healthy adaptations that permit them to survive unhealthy circumstances” (referred to in Bottrell, 2009, 325). Studies focusing on resilience among refugees and adults is limited, thus, our studies fill a gap in the field.

2.3.3. Coping

Coping, a term closely linked to resilience, can be defined as a process of managing the discrepancy between the demands of the situation and the available resources – a process that can alter the stressful problem or regulate the emotional response (Ahmadi et al. Forthcoming) or a process through which individuals attempt to understand and deal with important demands in their lives (Ganzevoort, 1998). People bring different resources to coping, such as material resources, physical resources, psychological resources (e.g., competence), social resources (e.g., interpersonal skills), spiritual (e.g., feeling close to God) (Pargament, 1997), or existential (e.g. feeling one with nature) (Ahmadi, 2015). Lazarus and Launier (1978) define coping as efforts, both action-oriented and intrapsychic, a person makes to manage (that is, master, tolerate, reduce, minimise) the environmental and internal demands, and the conflicts between them, that tax or exceed his/her resources. Pargament defines coping as a search for meaning in difficult times (Pargament, 1997). Meaning-making is a general human characteristic, and existential meaning refers to an individual's or a group's most essential meaning-making activity (DeMarinis, 2014).

Religious Coping

Religious coping as defined by Pargament, Smith, Koenig, Perez (1998) “is designed to assist people in the search for a variety of significant ends in stressful times: a sense of meaning and purpose, emotional comfort, personal control, intimacy with others, physical health, or spirituality” (Pargament et al. 1998, 711). When looking at religion/religiosity as a method for coping, it needs to be acknowledged that there are “two patterns of religious coping with potentially important implications for health”, that is negative and positive religious coping (Pargament et al. 1998, 712). In terms of positive religious coping, “social structures of religious groups” need to be considered (Loewenthal, 2007, 61) as these groups can provide social cohesion by offering rituals, routines and by representing a social support system which one can rely on in times of distress. The other factor that Loewenthal mentions is the “cognitive” dimension which alludes to “*automatic thoughts*” (Loewenthal, 2007, 61, emphasis in original). In this sense, beliefs can present a constant in the lives of people and/or also temporarily mobilise religious beliefs in times of crisis. Specifically in terms of mental health, Loewenthal asserts that “religious coping can be an effective buffer against anxiety states.” (Loewenthal, 2007, 69)

Positive and Negative Religious Coping

Religious coping itself was scaled into different forms by Pargament, Ensing, Falgout et al. 1990 (in Loewenthal, 2007, 61-62) and refers to positive religious coping such as attending religious services, feelings of having done what oneself could and leaving the rest to God, but also negative feelings such as anger with God and seeing the current situation as punishment by God, as well as religious avoidance, i.e. keeping oneself busy and distracting oneself by means of prayer or studying the bible (Loewenthal, 2007, 62, see also Pargament et al. 1998, 720). Consequently, “[d]ifferent forms of religious coping (...) have different implications for adjustment to critical life events.” (Pargament et al. 1998, 711). In this regard, studies have shown that participants perceived religion as a safe haven and that religion helped them to cope with depressive periods, affected their well-being and their self-esteem in a positive way (Maton, 1989, in Loewenthal, 2007, 62-63). Scientific literature has demonstrated “that there is a reliable association between many measures of religiosity and measures of well-being, including lowered distress and depression”. (Loewenthal, 2007, 59). In this regard, God was involved in coping, and religiosity/religion was used as a form of

compensation. Also, in a study by Schweitzer et al. (2007), religion was found to provide a source to regain control and meaning in life (Schweitzer et al. 2007, in Khanlou et al. in Simich & Andermann, 2014, 113). Loewenthal's research is undergirded by a study by Ahmadi and Ahmadi which presents religious coping methods in situations when feelings of stress and sadness take over (Ahmadi & Ahmadi, 2017).

2.4. Social-Ecological Model of Resilience

The importance of social contexts on the developmental trajectory of individuals needs to be acknowledged when analysing what accounts for and what affects resilience. In this sense, Michael Ungar has pointed out that in order "to understand resilience we must explore the context in which the individual experiences adversity, making resilience first a quality of the broader social and physical ecology, and second a quality of the individual" (Ungar, 2012, p. 27). Therefore, social-ecological factors such as education, interpersonal bonds, neighbourhood relations, community services and also structural factors such as citizenship, belonging and labour are focused on within this model. These factors are positioned at different levels/within different systems (micro-, meso-, macro-) and are framed by the individual system and the chrono-system.

2.4.1. Opportunities and Resources

Ungar (2012) points out that resilience should be regarded as an interactive two-way process, which is nurtured by external stimuli and at the same time depends on the individual's internal perception. Thus, this constant negotiation between the individual and their environment(s) is driven by opportunities which the individual is presented with and to which they respond to. These opportunities encompass resources (social, cultural, psychological, physical) which need to be available to and accessible for the individual (Ungar, 2012, 14). Additionally, these resources must be meaningful to the individual in order to help enhance resilience. Thus, if social and psychological determinants meet the needs/expectations/ideas of the individual, the environment ideally "facilitate[s] [...] resilience-promoting processes" (Ungar, 2012, 1). In other words, opportunity structures as part of the social-ecology influence the individual's ability in their experience of resilience and, vice-versa, the personal attributes of the individual influence his/her ability to access these resources if these are perceived as fitting/adequate and thereby meaningful. These resources are essential for the social-ecology framework and differ from person to person and from context to context, as they depend on the demands of the individual and the context one finds oneself in (Ungar, 2012, 18).

2.4.2. Social Determinants

In this report we focus on psychological and social determinants of health and their interactions. Two categories of social determinants are relevant: material variables, including a physically safe environment, housing, healthcare, education, economy, employment, and policies and interpersonal variables, including a sense of cultural, ethnic, or religious affiliation, social network, social support, trauma experiences, inclusion/exclusion interactions, discrimination, and social status (Cetrez et al., 2020; Hynie, 2018; Kirmayer, 2012). We also address culture-specific dimensions of social determinants such as the subjective meaning of determining factors based on culture, politics, and economy

(Kirmayer, 2012). Interactions of social determinants and aspects of resilience affect acculturation and well-being and health. Bringing social and cultural context(s) to the fore implies being aware of social norms and reactions in a given society. In several contemporary European countries, more so in the northern countries, gender equality, secular-rational worldviews (including post-secular expressions), and a high esteem of self-expression are predominant values (World Values Survey, 2018).

Our RESPOND-report (Cetrez et al., 2020) on integration policies, practices, and experiences, part of material variables referred to above, emphasises recent drastic changes of legislative measures, including a shift of focus from integration to individual establishment – where governments have made language acquisition and labour market integration the main focus of their integration policy. Further, while newcomers are welcome to participate in different educational programmes, segregation in housing has become a major challenge. Several studies reveal a link between post-migration experiences, for example, a long period as an asylum seeker (Laban et al., 2004) or being in detention during the asylum process (Steel, 2006) and high levels of PTSD.

Moving on to interpersonal variables, several studies have found that the weakening of social networks and lack of social support affect the mental health and quality of life of refugees (Gorst-Unsworth, Goldenberg, 1998; Laban et al., 2004; Gerritsen et al., 2006; Sundvall et al., 2020). In a review of studies on resettled war refugees, the impact of low social support is especially noticeable in association with depression (Bogic, Njoku & Priebe, 2015). In a Swedish study of refugees from Eritrea, Somalia, and Syria, 60-70% had low social support, which was associated with increased risk of depression, anxiety, PTSD as well as with low levels of self-rated well-being (Tinghög et al., 2016).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), “[d]eterminants of health are those factors that can enhance or threaten an individual’s or a community’s health status (WHO, 2004, 16). The multi-level framework of determinants of health (Mawani, in Simich & Andermann, 2014, 27-50) can be integrated into the social-ecology framework for resilience in the way that it exemplifies how differences in the trajectory of mental health depend on “inequalities in social determinants, including socioeconomic factors, social support, and systemic racism and discrimination.” (Mawani in Simich & Andermann, 2014, 28). These factors can be found on different levels such as macro-, community-, family-, and individual levels which resound with the levels offered in the social-ecological framework (Mawani, 2014, 28). Therefore, these can be regarded as being congruent with the systems presented earlier, whereas the family-level can be included into the micro-level and the community-level can be placed in both micro- and meso-level. According to Mawani, “[i]ntersecting dimensions of diversity” (Mawani, 2014, 27) determine mental health outcomes because there are “inequalities in mental health determinants” which exist among different groups such as native-born citizens, refugees/immigrants and also among different sub-groups of refugees (Mawani, 2014, 27).

Thus, “[t]he dynamic interactions of these factors operating at multiple levels affect mental health outcomes” (Mawani, 2014, 28). Consequently, the factors transactionally depend on one another and are in a constant change, reacting and adapting to ever-changing circumstances on multiple levels. Concerning macro-level factors, it becomes obvious that factors such as “economic, political, social and physical contexts” that refugees experienced before migration, influence their expectations of these contexts in their country of destination (Mawani, 2014, 29-30). If these factors are unstable or present a threat to the existence of the people, this can negatively influence their mental health.

2.4.3. The Seven D's and Psychological Health

The seven D's, as defined by McKenzie, Tuck and Agic (2014) are closely related to the availability of resources/opportunities. In this sense, they are "[t]he factors that have an impact on [the] psychological health of asylum-seekers" (McKenzie et al. 2014, 184). These factors include discrimination, detention, dispersal, destitution, delayed decisions, denial of the right to work, and denial of healthcare (McKenzie et al. 2014, 184 f.), which we will present here:

- Discrimination refers to the stigmatisation of refugees in host countries and includes cheap propaganda by politicians and media.
- Detention along with the non-safeguarding of access to health services while in detention threatens the psychological well-being of asylum-seekers.
- Dispersal refers to scattering of refugees/refugee camps to different parts of the country and this includes having to move several times with no voice in the choice of relocation, this potentially "destabilise[s] development of social networks".
- Destitution is concerned with the poverty and adversity that refugee applicants face in many countries as they "receive the lowest levels of income support."
- Delayed decisions refers to the lengthy and weary processes of refugee application.
- The denial of the right to work refers to the restrictions to work which can "inhibit social integration and increase poverty."
- The denial of healthcare refers to the fact that "[i]n many countries there are limits to access to services for refugee applicants and those whose applications fail."

All of the seven D's affect the mental well-being of asylum-seekers negatively due to the restrictions, set-backs, isolation, uncertainty, destabilisation, marginalisation, and worry accompanying the factors.

2.4.4. Systems and Levels

As mentioned above, the resources that are tackled within the social-ecological framework are subdivided into five different systems which stem from Urie Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory (1979, in Panter-Brick & Eggerman, 2012, 371). As "nested levels of influence", they are integrated within one another and as such, the systems are permeable and non-demarcated (Tol et al. in Panter-Brick & Eggerman, 2012, 371). The systems are presented briefly in the following (Tol et al. in Panter-Brick, Eggerman, 2012, 372).

- The systems are layered around the individual system, which is positioned closest to the person and which is made up of personal qualities (such as intelligence/creativity) and ideological commitment but also includes personal coping strategies.
- The second level is the micro-system which is made up of the individual's most immediate environment(s) such as their closest relationships and social support systems, such as family connectedness and peer relations.
- The third level, the meso-/exo-system, encompasses the reciprocation of the different micro-systems, such as family-school interactions and health-system connectedness.
- The fourth system is the macro-system which includes the cultural practices and cultural resources as well as religious and political institutions.
- At the most extensive level, the systems are framed by the chrono-system which is the temporal dimension of the model (Schoon, 2012, 147; Damon & Lerner, 2006). As such, it refers to central turning points within an individual life time such as

transitions from one life phase to another which influence relationships, interactions and individual behaviour. Another dimension of the chrono-system is based within “the embeddedness of individual development in a specific socio-historical context” (Schoon, 2012, 147). This also needs to be regarded with close attention to opportunities as these depend on different contexts such as political and cultural ones within specific periods, and therefore depend on “sociocultural conditions that exist in a given historical period, and by how these evolve over time.” (Schoon, 2012, 147).

2.4.5. Meaning-Making and Individual Perception

However, it has been mentioned and needs to be highlighted, that resilience is framed by both social determinants (such as education, housing, health, citizenship/belonging) and psychological determinants (individual perception, behaviour, meaning-making). Hence, the perception of the individual is to be regarded as the psychological dimension of the concept. This refers to how the individual understands, receives and makes meaning of the resources offered. In this way, the crucial interplay between the social determinants that the individual is confronted with and the psychological determinants within the individual becomes apparent. Thus, factors from the outside and the perception from the inside act interdependently.

“Meaning making’ designates the process by which people interpret situations, events, objects, or discourses, in the light of their previous knowledge and experience.” (Zittoun & Brinkmann, 2012, 1809). As stated above, it is crucial to emphasise that the resources need to be provided in a meaningful way. This meaning is culture-specific and basically refers to the fact that the meaningfulness needs to be evident to the individual and needs to match his/her needs which e.g. depends on their socialisation, respectively “their previous knowledge and experience” (Zittoun & Brinkmann, 2012, 1809).

Thus, meaning refers to the system which signals individuals and communities the importance of certain factors for their life, or at least for certain areas in their lives such as e.g. well-being. As a consequence, this meaning determines the decision for and against specific resources as well as the ability to determine what is meaningful, i.e. what is needed for positive development. According to Ungar, this meaning system is culturally constructed (Ungar, 2012, 22) and essential because it accompanies people along their stations in life and is closely related to issues of identity. Ungar goes on by pointing out that it guides people in what they perceive as purposeful actions and as “to which resources (opportunities) they value and access” (Ungar, 2012, 22). Nevertheless, this meaning is also evident in the macro system as the resources provided depend on the meaning that is attributed to them, usually indicated by the dominant culture within a specific socio-cultural, socio-historical and time-specific context. Thus, “the opportunities that we create” (Ungar 2012, 22) are always bound by context.

This assumption also highlights the fact that individuals are not seen as passive but of course do play their part in the interplay of social-ecology and individual behaviour. Thus, ecology and individuals find themselves in an interactive and reciprocal relation, whereas externally available and accessible resources mobilise personal strengths internally. It is then the “*congruence* between individual needs and environments” which is crucial for positive personal development (Ungar, 2012, 15, emphasis added). Once opportunities (such as support systems) are offered, the individual can make use of them and draw from them by building up their own ability to cope. It also entails the capacity to negotiate for

resources, implying the active nature of individuals to stand up for their needs and for the resources they feel need to be provided. As Bronfenbrenner puts it: “the developing person is viewed not merely as a tabula rasa on which the environment makes its impact, but as a growing, dynamic entity that progressively moves into and restructures the milieu in which it resides.” (1979, 21).

Existential meaning is here understood through DeMarinis’ approach, focusing on “the individual’s understanding of existentiality and the way meaning is created [... including] worldview conception, life approach, decision-making structure, way of relating, and way of understanding” (DeMarinis, 2006, p.44-45). Religious teachings recognise the transcendental meaning of suffering and the fact that suffering, such as agony, despair, pain and conflict, belongs to the totality of life (Rhi, 2001). During and after traumatic events, individuals frequently report great cognitive dissonance between what they observe and experience in reality and what they previously believed were stable, secure, and predictable relationships, not only with other individuals but also with the supernatural or the metaphysical (Boehnlein, 1987).

2.5. The ADAPT Model

The Adaptation and Development after Persecution and Trauma (ADAPT) model was developed by psychiatrist Derrick Silove and offers an instrument to conceptualise policies and practices concerning “psychosocial interventions needed to assist populations exposed to mass conflict.” (Silove, 2013, 237). The model emanates from the notion that there are five “core psychosocial pillars” inherent to solid societies (Silove, 2013, 237). These interdependent pillars (1) Safety/Security, (2) Bonds/Networks, (3) Justice, (4) Roles and Identities, (5) Existential Meaning are essentially disrupted in the face of mass conflict, whereas a stabilisation of all pillars is needed “to restore stability to conflict affected societies.” (Silove, 2013, 245). As the social-ecology framework for resilience, the ADAPT model highlights the importance of the ecology of the individual and the role of social determinants which surround the individual.

Pillar 1 - Safety/Security: concerns the constant threat which individuals are being exposed to in situations of ongoing conflict and which affects their sense of security, stability and individual control, thereby disclosing perceived helplessness (Silove, 2013, 238). In this regard, the model highlights the importance of the setting which the individual is embedded in post-conflict, specifically if survivors of conflict and human rights violations have been confronted with “ongoing conditions of threat, uncertainty about the future, lack of control over their lives and an absence of social support or resources to achieve recovery” (Silove, 2013, 241). It becomes clear that the extreme circumstances that refugees had to endure during their migration journey as well as the experiences which made them leave their country as much as the precarious conditions in which they find themselves as newcomers to a new society, aggravate feelings of insecurity. Examples in this regard are manifold and pervade most areas that have been investigated in the RESPOND country reports such as education, labour, housing etc. In this context, threats and uncertainties mentioned in one area, consequently influence uncertainties/insecurities in other areas.

Pillar 2 - Bonds and Networks: concerns the extensive personal losses that are born out of conflict. Therefore, grieving for lost bonds and interpersonal connections and networks due to displacement, separation and fatalities presents an enormous adversity and can lead to developing mental disorders such as depression (Silove, 2013, 241). Restoring

interpersonal bonds through family reunification can help to recover from “a wide range of emotional disorders following exposure to conflict” and should therefore be made focus of strategies to promote relief (Silove, 2013, 242). In addition, mourning rituals specific to a certain culture can also help to cope in times of grieving, and psychosocial programmes can support recovery of grieving individuals in precarious social conditions (in which newcomers oftentimes find themselves) such as unaccompanied minors (Silove, 2013, 242).

Pillar 3 - Justice: describes the psychological dimension of feelings of injustice. In this regard, it has been assessed that the sense of unresolved injustice(s) of past experiences can lead to psychological disorders “following exposure to persecution and human rights violations” (Silove, 2013, 242). While, broadly speaking, anger can be regarded as a normative response to injustice, “pattern of explosive anger” can be developed as an extreme response and can be reflected in attacks of anger “triggered by minor events” (Silove, 2013, 242). This can have grave social consequences for the individual as well as for their closest environment and for the wider community that the individual belongs to. Programmes aiming at promoting mental health and psychosocial support programmes can help to restore “an ethos of justice” through conveying “a sense of acknowledgement, dignity, respect and empowerment.” (Silove, 2013, 243).

Pillar 4 - Roles and Identities: refers to the impact that conflict and displacement/resettlement has on personal roles in interpersonal relations such as within families, the wider community and society in general (Silove, 2013, 243). Threats to personal roles can also play into challenging feelings of identity (Silove, 2013, 243). The uncertainty as well as the unbearable adversities that accompany mass conflict, can tremendously harm an individual’s sense of identity. This is added upon by precarious conditions in post-migration when migrants find themselves in camps, hot spots and in societies which are unwelcoming towards newcomers (Silove, 2013, 243). Pillar 4 can thus be challenged by unemployment and discrimination acting out in exclusion and discrimination. Establishing a coherent sense of self and the inherent roles to this self can thus be fundamentally questioned and culminate in “[i]dentity confusion” (Silove, 2013, 243). On a micro-level, implications of this can be an impairment of family cohesion and on a wider level can be a lowered level of social acceptance. In turn, this can further aggravate feelings of isolation. In this sense, social determinants can support the re-establishment of a coherent sense of self (by adopting new roles and by developing hybrid identities) after migration through for example, meaningful work (Silove, 2013, 243). Sustaining community structures and cohesive patterns within the family can be regarded as an adaptive response to struggles in post-migration settings which can derive from a change of social structure (Silove, 2013, 243).

Pillar 5 - Existential meaning: refers to the broader narrative that individuals situate themselves in, such as world views and systems of beliefs. It is self-evident that these are affected by the broader social and cultural frame that encapsulates the individual’s life. In times of conflict and experiences of displacement, these views and systems are disrupted by being resettled into contexts with divergent systems of beliefs, such as from a monotheistic society to one in which a variety of faiths is practised (Silove, 2013, 244). In consequence, fears of being restricted in cultural and religious practices in the society of resettlement can accompany doubts and increase these. Furthermore, one can face a dilemma, by means of feeling caught between different systems which on the one hand can complicate settling in the new country and on the other hand can lead to existential struggles regarding the world view that one has had for most of his/her life. Sensitive approaches, by both policy makers,

service providers such as caretakers need to be taken so that accommodation to the new culture and possibly diverse world views can evolve (Silove, 2013, 244).

2.6. Summary

The different theoretical models and specific concepts presented so far in this report will guide us in analysing the psychosocial health conditions and outcomes in the empirical material as presented in different country reports. Thus, for the purpose of summarising as well as bringing together the central concepts, the figure below depicts our approach. The social-ecological model of resilience is structured along the individual as the inner or intrapersonal system, and micro, meso, and macro as the outer or interpersonal systems. Each system is specified by the relevant determinants. They also affect each other, meaning, one change in any of these will result in a possible change in the other (small arrows). The meaning-system cuts across the other systems, indicating a balancing function in the model. The ADAPT model is also relevant for the resilience model with its five pillars, safety/security, bonds and networks, justice, roles and identities along with existential meaning (in the figure inserted in relation to relevant systems, in bold and italic). The ADAPT model is specified by challenges the newcomers are facing and their responses, adaptive or extreme.

In the next chapter, the empirical material is presented along the systems in the social-ecological model of resilience for each RESPOND-country, starting with policies of health on the macro level, followed by institutional contact and stakeholder experiences on the meso level, and the individual experiences of newcomers on the micro level. Furthermore, relevant social and psychological determinants are presented, ending with individual coping methods. The final chapter uses the ADAPT model to further analyse the empirical material.

Figure 2 A socio-ecological model of resilience together with the ADAPT-model

Note: The small arrow lines indicate that the systems affect each other. The longer arrow line indicates that the meaning-system cuts across all other systems and has a balancing function.

3. Resilience, Coping, Psycho-Social Health and the Role of Religion in RESPOND-countries

The following section summarises the different health issues among newcomers in the RESPOND-countries (Sweden, UK, Germany, Austria, Poland, Italy, Hungary, Greece, Turkey, Iraq). Material is taken from the country reports.² Every country will reflect a three paragraph division, the policy level (macro level) the institutional contact and stakeholder experience (meso level) and newcomers' experiences (micro level). The policy level will outline the legal context of the country and the most important laws concerning migration issues. This will be followed by the institutional contact and stakeholder experience with attention on the health services as experienced by providers, participation of non-state institutions, cultural, gender and contextual factors. Finally, when analysing newcomers' experiences the report will focus on resilience and coping methods and on meaning-making mechanisms.

² For full reports, see respective country reports referred to:

Sweden: Cetrez, O., DeMarinis, V., Pettersson, J. and Shakra, M. (2020, July 19). Integration Policies, Practices and Experiences – Sweden Country Report (Version v.1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3951714>

UK: Atto, N., Hirst, C. and Hall, V. (2020, July 14). Integration Policies, Practices and Experiences – United Kingdom Country Report (Version v.1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3945509>

Germany: Chemin, J.E. and Nagel, A.K. (2020, June 3). Integration Policies, Practices and Experiences – Germany Country Report (Version v.1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3874426>

Austria: Josipovic, I. and Reeger, U. (2020, June 17). Integration Policies, Practices and Experiences – Austria. Country Report (Version v.1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3898430>

Poland: Sobczak-Szelc, K., Pachocka, M., Pędziwiatr, K. and Szałańska, J. (2020, August 30). Integration Policies, Practices and Experiences – Poland Country Report (Version v.1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4008666>

Italy: Ibrido, R. and Marchese, C. (2020, June 15). Integration Policies, Practices and Experiences–Italy. Country Report (Version v.1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3894103>

Greece: Leivaditi, N., Papatzani, E., Ilias, A. and Petracou, E. (2020, June 9). Integration Policies, Practices and Experiences – Greece Country Report (Version v.1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3886993>

Turkey: Rottmann, S.B. (2020, May 30). Integration Policies, Practices and Experiences – Turkey Country Report (Version v.1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3865824>

Iraq: Warda, W.K. and Almaffraji, H.S. (2020, September 8). Integration Policies, Practices and Experiences – Iraq Country Report (Version v.1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4019804>

3.1. Sweden

3.1.1 National level of healthcare - Macro system

The health care possibilities for newcomers in Sweden are regulated through the Acts that provide health and emergency care for Asylum Seekers (Socialstyrelsen, 2019). The Act regulates the rights and access of the asylum seekers, beneficiaries of protection and certain other newcomers to the Swedish healthcare system. This act contains provisions that offer healthcare and dental care to asylum seekers, beneficiaries of protection and to certain other foreigners. Asylum seekers are also entitled to reproductive healthcare via the Swedish Communicable Disease Act. Undocumented migrants on the other hand, fall under regulatory Acts (2013, 407, Government Bill 2012/13, 109) which provide emergency care, somatic and psychiatric healthcare and dental care (Socialstyrelsen, 2019). In the country policies regarding pre- and post-migration public health and public mental health are taken into consideration to deal with integration matters.

As highlighted in the country report (Cetrez et al., 2020), in 2015 Sweden witnessed a major influx of asylum seekers and the healthcare system lacked proper means to deal with this. In particular, the need for information, difficulties in communication, the lack of interpreters, the lack of cultural understanding and competence, the special needs of unaccompanied minors and the need to meet the requirements of mental health treatment were some of these issues. In addition, displacement and housing of asylum seekers, great distance from the healthcare centres and equality between genders of the staff, were very important points that required further attention.

3.1.2. Institutional level of healthcare - Meso system

In Sweden, there is a significant effort to understand and analyse the psychological health of newcomers. At the meso-level, it is important to highlight the role of NGOs and of the Red Cross in particular. For example, churches of different denominations in Sweden have focused their support on newly arrived migrants, without differentiation of religious affiliation, mainly around needs of housing, finding work, social activities, and general societal information for an effective integration. Religious and ethnic organisations among migrants have an advantage in counselling newcomers, as their members have prior migration experience and are thus able to support the newcomers linguistically as well as with social and practical issues in life in general. For example, churches of different denominations in Sweden have focused their support on newly arrived migrants, without differentiation of religious affiliation, mainly around needs of housing, finding work, social activities, and general societal information for an effective integration. Religious and ethnic organisations among migrants have an advantage in counselling newcomers, as their members have prior migration experience and are thus able to support the newcomers linguistically as well as with social and practical issues in life in general.

3.1.3. Individual psychosocial health - Micro system

Coping is mainly associated with the support of family (spouse, partner, and children) as a significant factor, as it serves as a good support system and helps newcomers to settle better into their new country.

Access to psychological and healthcare was possible and functional among most interviewees. However, when it came to mental health counselling the service was avoided by newcomers. The main reasons were the lack of confidence and trust towards strangers. In addition, there was evidence of problems with interpretation, shortage of interpreters, lack of expertise among interpreters, or problems in identifying the language or dialect when booking an interpreter prior to a counselling, resulting in delays or having an interpreter not able to translate. This raised problems of language discrimination and feelings of rejection connected to perceived discrimination (Cetrez et al. 2020, 103).

In addition, it is important to highlight the role of NGOs. For example, churches of different denominations in Sweden have focused their support on newly arrived migrants, without differentiation of religious affiliation, mainly around needs of housing, finding work, social activities, and general societal information for an effective integration. Religious and ethnic organisations among migrants have an advantage in counselling newcomers, as their members have prior migration experience and are thus able to support the newcomers linguistically as well as with social and practical issues in life in general.

Meaning making: Mostly mentioned as meaning-giving factors were children, friends, religion, family, community, work, and self-fulfilment.

Children: Children seem to be the strongest meaning-giving factor for many participants, being a source of happiness, giving motivation, hope, goals in life, pride, and optimism. This is followed by family including spouse and partner giving purpose, support, motivation, optimism, and care.

Sometimes I feel very depressed, but when I see my children, especially my daughter, when she is running to me and calling my name, I feel so much better. The only problem I feel is when I think about the rejections, but I'm not a sad or depressed person. (Afghan man, Age group 18-26, No.51, Asylum seeker, Cetrez et al. 2020)

Friends: Friends are deemed as supportive and helpful in a practical and emotional sense in the new life in Sweden.

Religion: The role of religion is a central factor across immigrants, yielding positive or negative outcomes to different situations and individuals. In positive situations, religion has helped with psychological and emotional support and strength.

The difficulties that I had in my life in the past were very severe. A lot of things happened to my family, to my father, brother and my mom, things that happened to me. But still I have hope that God will always be with me, if I am always thinking positively. And now it's much better and there is a God. (Afghan man, Age group 27-50, No.50, Asylum seeker, Cetrez et al. 2020)

For some, religion has also provided a means for improving social connections as they also form social bonds with Swedes. In negative situations, religion has hindered an individual's psychological wellbeing as it mitigates seeking psychosocial help in terms of actions like therapy, and can unmitigated be a source of apathy, flight from reality and engaging in self-destructive behaviour.

Family: The support of family (spouse, partner, and children) is a factor in immigrant health, as it serves as a good support system and helps immigrants in their integration to

settle better into their new country. However, in a few cases, family can also have negative effects connected to the environment resulting from the legal status of the newcomers.

It has changed a lot, positively and negatively. Positive is that we are supporting each other. When we are sad we are talking to each other, telling each other everything, helping each other. But nobody has patience. When we talk about something, we fight with each other, talk very loud and scream at each other. We don't have patience anymore, because of the situation that we are living in. (Afghan woman, Age group 18-26, No.55, Asylum seeker in deportation stage, Cetrez et al. 2020)

Other meaning-giving factors were *communities*, such as ethnic clubs, bringing people closer to each other, as well as hindering negative outcomes such as depression and even suicide. *Work* was also expressed as meaning-giving, strengthening participants' self-image, as being ambitious and successful. Self-fulfilment underlines the value of goals in life, respect, pride, and gender equality.

3.1.4. Social and psychological determinants

The quantitized Swedish interview material (Cetrez & Barthoma, 2020) showed that, in terms of serious illness, less than one out of ten interviewees reported to have been affected. Approximately the same share reported that they were tortured and again about the same share experienced rape or other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence. One third reported violence at the border. Gender based violence was reported by a very small number of participants.

A little more than one in five got a rejection at the first instance. As for the rejection at the second instance, one third got a rejection and a little more than one in ten cases were still pending. In the Swedish case, slightly fewer than one in three reported that their general experience with the engagement with national authorities/actors to seek protection or status determination was (rather) not supportive. Concerning the general experience of the engagement with NGOs, regarding seeking protection, about one in seven experienced this as (rather) not supportive.

In Sweden, a little less than half of the interviewees stayed in decentralised accommodation. Concerning perceived tensions with security personnel, about one fifth expressed this. Moreover, the majority declared they had received basic health care. A little less than two thirds declared having received childcare support. The vast majority (about four in five) specified having attended a language class. Two thirds attended a vocational course or training. Moreover, the majority (more than three out of four) declared that their general experience with reception administrators was (rather) supportive.

Concerning housing, the majority (three out of five) of the respondents were able to choose their own housing/facility in Sweden. In addition, most of the interviewees (a little less than three in four) were satisfied with the region they were living in at the time of the interview. About two in five of the respondents were working to earn money at the time of the interview and a little more than half of the respondents reported to have experienced some kind of discrimination in the Swedish labour market. Approximately three quarters of the respondents in Sweden declared they experienced a very difficult situation, such as a serious accident, natural catastrophe, rape, war, abuse, torture. About two thirds expressed

psychological ill-health at the time of the interview. At the same time, about one fourth expressed physical ill-health. Most of the interviewees expressed a capability for resilience or coping (such as adaption, handling, bouncing back, having resources or similar after illness or hardship). Slightly more than half characterised their relationship with their neighbours in Sweden as close and friendly.

3.2 The United Kingdom

3.2.1 National level of healthcare - Macro system

According to the UK country report (Atto et al. 2020), at the macro level, every person in the United Kingdom (UK), irrespective of immigration is able to access emergency and accident services, free GP services for primary health care, and treatment for specific diseases (Atto et al, 2020, 69). Refugees have free access to health care under the NHS, and asylum seekers with current asylum claims can access healthcare through registration with a General Practice (Asylum Information Database, 2019, 74). Refused asylum seekers with an outstanding application and in receipt of Section 95 or Section 4 support can still register with a General Practitioner. Despite these laws and policies at the macro level, asylum seekers and refused asylum seekers still find difficulties in accessing the UK health system which is extremely complicated with regulations subject to frequent changes (Asylum Information Database, 2019, 74).

3.2.2. Institutional level of healthcare - Meso system

In the UK country report (Atto et al., 2020), the different levels of immigrant integration are based on the meso- level, referring to practices and on the micro-level, addressing experiences. According to the report, the UK witnessed a fragmented, conflicting, short-sighted policy-making and a hostile environment to migrants, especially asylum seekers. The most persistent areas of difficulty as underlined by stakeholders, refugees and asylum seekers are psychological health and physical wellbeing. The asylum process is the main factor of stress for newcomers in the country, leading to health issues and the prohibition of effective healthcare intervention (Atto et al., 2020, 80). In particular, the ineffective support and a lack of regard for vulnerability – in the context of detention and deportation – has caused increasing issues with mental health and wellbeing.

A middle-aged Iranian man explains how governmental policy and associated legal processes have impacted his mental health while in the UK:

I would like to work but can't now, because of my depression. ... [M]y physical issues are all from Iran but my emotional/mental state has become worse here. ... They gave me a court date for after a year then and it got cancelled also once or twice so it took 1.5 year to get a reply and so it affected my emotional, mental state quite a lot. ... I was getting scared of what they would decide. The more I heard about other people's experiences of the courts, I got more scared and I was lonely too. ... I was alone at home constantly and thinking about things a lot and so became a little depressed then. ... I am not so well these days either. (Interview 22, Atto et al. 2020)

3.2.3. Individual psychosocial health - Micro system

The UK report (Atto et al., 2020) states that post-migration stressors also have a decisive impact on people's further integration into the host society. Problems surrounding security, safety and integration have often been identified as key elements. Isolation is one of them and it contributes to increased psychosocial difficulties. This can be understood as a symptom of previous traumas experienced in the country of origin or during the migration process. The trauma responses that occurred once in the UK are certainly not seen as restricted to individuals held in detention, or to individuals who had experienced detention. For example, deportation is identified as a permanent or potential threat and frequently understood as inevitable within the asylum seeker and refugee communities. In fact, trauma is consistently identified within more settled groups. It is frequently expressed as an evident barrier towards integration. A respondent described how reconnection with his wife has resolved his 'difficult situation' of isolation within the UK:

So I had quite a difficult situation here, until the weather improved, it became warmer and my wife arrived from Iran ... Well the important person is my wife, and no one else really. Mum and Dad have become like zombies really because of Islam their soul is dead. The good thing about my wife is that she motivates me, says to me, 'don't give up'. I didn't have anyone else to support me, who did I have [?] ... She has annoyed me a lot but as the proverb goes, your teacher's beating is like a whisper of love' (laughter), excuse me. ... We quarrel as well even over important matters but then carry on the next day and don't have anyone else either, just each other. (Interview 24, Atto et al., 2020)

Moreover, what seems to have the most serious effect on psychosocial health as highlighted in the country report, (Atto et al., 2020) is the perception of being separated from family and/or concern for one's safety, as well as a fear of not being able to see their family again. These are sources of *meaning-making* and many newcomers explain how connection with their family, family security and support and marital intimacy, are the most powerful resources in counteracting the psychosocial impact of isolation, insecurity, anxiety, and lack of integration in the UK (Atto et al., 2020). As a matter of fact, separation from family is the major cause of mental ill-health and feelings of isolation among newcomers in the UK.

Among UK respondents, what has been identified as supporting a positive systemic change and improved psychosocial health for asylum seekers and refugees are decreased waiting times, access to community, to networks, or to one's cultural group, connections to family, a facilitation of 'hope' and increased access to sufficient psychological care and assistance (Atto et al., 2020).

3.2.4. Social and psychological determinants

The quantitized UK interview material (Cetrez & Barthoma, 2020) showed that the most distinct feature in the UK is that more than one in four of the interviewees expressed to have been arrested at the border. The same number of respondents said to have been detained at the border and almost one third of the interviewees expressed to have experienced detention in a detention facility in the UK.

About three in five got a rejection at the first instance, whereas two in three got a rejection at the second instance and the decision for one in six was still pending. In the UK, a little more than two in three said that their general experience with the engagement with

national authorities/actors to seek protection or status determination was (rather) not supportive. The general experience with the engagement with NGOs regarding to seek protection was (rather) not supportive for one in seven.

In the UK, the majority (more than four in five) stayed in decentralised accommodation. About half of the interviewees mentioned perceived tensions with security personnel. All of the interviewees declared having received basic healthcare. A little less than half expressed to have received childcare support. All of the interviewees answered the question of having attended a language class in the affirmative. The UK experience with reception administrators was in general not supportive, with more than two in three answering they had perceived the administrators as (rather) not supportive.

Three in four of the respondents were able to choose their own housing/facility in the UK. Additionally, approximately four in five answered they are satisfied with the region they are living in. About two in five of the respondents specified they are working to earn money and two in three experienced some kind of discrimination in the labour market. Slightly more than half attended a vocational course or training. In the UK, almost all of the respondents declared they had experienced a very difficult situation, such as a serious accident, natural catastrophe, rape, war, abuse, torture. Furthermore, almost all of the interviewees reported psychological ill-health at the time of the interview. Also, three in four expressed physical ill-health. All of the respondents expressed an ability for showing resilience or coping. Two in three specified their relationships with their neighbours in the UK as close and friendly.

3.3 Poland

3.3.1. National level of healthcare - Macro system

According to the Polish country report (Sobczak-Szelc et al., 2020) the constitution of the Republic of Poland granted in 1997 that 'Everyone shall have the right to have his health protected'. This indicates universal access to healthcare without distinguishing between citizens and foreigners. However, when it came to access to healthcare in the country, the major issues that rose in interviews with newcomers were: difficult access to specialists, long waiting lists for specialised treatments, or necessity to use the private sector and pay for such services. Moreover, when experiencing access to medical treatments, the barriers that were pointed out were mainly addressing the linguistic and intercultural incompetencies of medical personnel.

3.3.2. Institutional level of healthcare - Meso system

At the meso level, the role of NGOs is of particular importance in providing access to health resources (Sobczak-Szelc et al., 2020). The main contributions of the sector can be identified in the provision of supplementary psychological assistance to persons with international protection. However, NGOs have been negatively affected due to financial difficulties of some of the organisations providing this type of assistance since 2015.

The second trend has been the role of religion among migrants. Despite the highly religious homogeneity of Poland with over 80% adhering to the Catholic Church (Sobczak-Szelc et al. 2020), religious communities have been playing an important role in shaping attitudes towards migration and certain groups of migrants. However, religious discrimination

was highlighted, among which physical attacks addressed to women wearing hijabs or in the context of hospital treatment. However, it was shown that one does not need to be a Muslim, but it is enough to “look Muslim” to face some forms of aggressions from officials or authorities linked with anti-Muslim racism.

Institutionally, religious organisations have also been participating in the processes of their integration in the country. Some organisations tried to ease integration. An example is the Catholic organisation which has been actively helping asylum seekers and refugees regardless of their religious affiliation for many years.

Moreover, when experiencing access to medical treatments, the barriers that were pointed out were mainly addressing the linguistic and intercultural incompetencies of medical personnel.

Some interviewees pointed out the difficulty of sharing without knowing the language and the consequent psychological closure. *‘I was suffering because of the language, frankly, communicating with him was difficult because of the language’*. Some others also resorted to secondary means to cope with their problems: *‘[.but] if I don’t understand something completely, I look for the answers on the internet’*. (PLMIUK19, Sobczak-Szelc et al., 2020)

Based on the report (Sobczak-Szelc et al. 2020), a policy that was adopted to try to face the challenge was the accompaniment of the refugee by a translator. This linguistic help seemed to be of particular importance in granting better access when it came to psychological assistance. However, it was pointed out that there is still a consistent lack of specialised treatments for victims of torture or traumatized asylum seekers and refugees. These are not available in practice in Poland because of a lack of qualified psychologists and therapists specializing in treating trauma, in particular in an intercultural context. In general, newcomers were overall satisfied with the healthcare provisions that they received. Yet, at the micro level, some interviewees underlined the time delays and long waiting periods. In addition, experiences of discrimination and unjust treatment in hospital settings were highlighted in some interviews:

I’ve experienced discrimination in the hospital. It was my first time in the Polish hospital and I didn’t know what to do. [...] When it was my turn one woman approached me and said: ‘You are a refugee, so for you the entrance is prohibited. Go home and treat yourself there’. It was just the first shocking experience. (PLMICH10, Sobczak-Szelc et al., 2020)

3.3.3. Individual psychosocial health - Micro system

The Polish country report (Sobczak-Szelc et al. 2020) states that religion has been playing an important role for existential meaning-making for migrants and exists as a resource from which they draw when facing problems, including psychological ones. It provides them with a sense of stability and continuity at the time when they are often deprived of these key elements of psychological well-being. The positive religious practices cited are prayers. Religion is also seen as facilitating bonding and bridging contributing to integration.

Yes, I am religious, my religion is Islam (...) We pray every day and do everything, what is necessary. No matter where you are, you should remember, who you are. (PLMICH02, Sobczak-Szelc et al., 2020)

Among the cultural barriers that influence practices there is the attitude of Chechens towards psychological help. In the country, the negative conception of being 'mentally ill' is still connected to the positive effort of asking for help. This creates an uneasy situation for newcomers that are actually aware of the help that they can get from a psychologist but maybe less prone to reach out for it due to the cultural difference in the welcoming country and community.

3.3.4. Social and psychological determinants

The quantitized Polish interview material (Cetrez & Barthoma, 2020), regarding vulnerability, showed that one fifth of the respondents expressed to be single parents with minor children. Also, about one in eight expressed they were tortured and one tenth experienced violence at the border. More than one third stated they had been detained in Poland, whereas about one in four said they had been detained in a detention facility.

Almost half got a rejection at the first instance, whereas slightly less than two in five got a rejection at the second instance and the decision for one in four was still pending. In Poland, one in three mentioned that their general experience of the engagement with national authorities/actors to seek protection or status determination was (rather) not supportive. The general experience with the engagement with NGOs regarding to seek protection was described by one in ten as (rather) not supportive.

In Poland, the majority (slightly less than four in five) stayed in decentralised accommodation. A very small number reported to have perceived tensions with security personnel. Also, all indicated to have received basic healthcare. About two thirds mentioned having received childcare support. About two thirds answered they had attended a language class. About one third attended a vocational course or training in Poland. The general experience with reception administrators in Poland was over all (rather) supportive, with approximately every three in four claiming to have perceived the administrators as (rather) supportive.

About three out of five reported to have been able to choose their own housing/facility in Poland. About four in five claimed to be satisfied with the region they are living in. A little more than half of the respondents specified they are working to earn money and slightly less than one in five experienced some kind of discrimination in the labour market. About two thirds declared they experienced a very difficult situation, for example a serious accident, natural catastrophe, rape, war, abuse, torture. Additionally, approximately two in three expressed psychological ill-health at the time of the interview. Moreover, a little more than half expressed physical ill-health. Four in five expressed an ability for resilience or coping. Slightly more than half characterised their relationships with their neighbours in Poland as close and friendly.

3.4 Greece

3.4.1. National level of healthcare - Macro system

As per the Greek country report (Leivaditi et al., 2020). The Greek healthcare system is a mixed model of both tax-based financing and social health insurance. At the macro level, there is no substantive healthcare legislation. This is because the healthcare system has

historically grappled with enduring structural and operational inadequacies that have not yet been addressed. The recent monetary crisis and the severe fiscal constraints crisis has further exacerbated the failure or stagnation of health reforms (Economou et al., 2017).

As the Greek report on health highlights (Leivaditi et al. 2020, 54) , there have been policies implemented to provide healthcare to asylum seekers in the form of the “PHILOS – Emergency health response to refugee crisis” as a parallel health care programme for refugees and migrants. The programme is supported by the Greek Ministry of Health and implemented by the National Organisation of Public Health. The programme exists to address the refugee crisis by attending to the sanitary and psychosocial needs of people living in reception centres by responding comprehensively to the urgent situation caused by the refugee crisis in mainland Greece (Attica, Northern and Central Greece) after the closure of the Greek-North Macedonia borders and the EU-Turkey Statement, which resulted in a large number of refugees being stranded in the country and living in open camps created by the Greek government.

3.4.2. Institutional level of healthcare - Meso system

As the Greek report on health indicates (Leivaditi et al., 2020), psychosocial support services in Greece are not easily accessible for refugees and asylum seekers due to the limited capacity of the public sector in terms of intercultural competence, staff shortages and lack of proper infrastructure. Access to healthcare services appears to be particularly difficult in the overcrowded reception camps, especially on the Aegean Islands, where the responsibilities for health services were transferred from NGOs to state actors in 2017. A series of recent reports indicate that many asylum seekers suffer from depression and post-traumatic disorders, leading to increasing suicide attempts and self-harm, also among young people (Leivadititi et al., 2020). Stress, anxiety, insomnia, nightmares, loss of hope and fear are among the depressive feelings evoked by many asylum seekers living in the Reception and Identification Centres, according to the Greek report. Regarding medical care and psychosocial support, most of the interviewees in these centres reported the serious lack of state presence as well as the serious shortages facing medical services, both in the Hotspot of Moria and on the rest of the island.

We receive so many cases that cannot be examined in Moria for lack of capacity... but we also must serve a big part of the Greek population. Of course, we will also attend to refugees. But when the number is so large... (Public Hospital doctor in Mytilene, Leivaditi et al., 2020)

3.4.3. Individual psychosocial health - Micro system

The Greek report (Leivaditi et al., 2020) reveals that the long waiting times, delays for an appointment with doctors and the general lack of medical support can be life-threatening for asylum seekers, especially for those with chronic diseases. Again, language barriers are found to be major determinants of stress in newcomers. As a matter of fact, immigrants denounced the lack of access to interpreters during their appointments with doctors.

In addition, the inhuman living conditions of the reception facilities have a serious impact on newcomer’s physical and mental health.

If you are not sick, healthy, ... mentally or physically, if someone is not sick, he is healthy. If you are coming from your country healthy, when you arrive here and you see this situation, how you live, how you get food, how you make your interview, how they treat you, immediately you are (become) sick mentally or physically. (Robel, Male, Migrant, Economou et al., 2017)

3.4.4. Social and psychological determinants

The quantitized Greece interview material (Cetrez & Barthoma, 2020) showed that in terms of vulnerability, a very small number of women indicated they were pregnant during the migration journey. In addition, very significantly, almost one fifth expressed to have been tortured and even more, a bit more than one third expressed to have been raped and/or experienced other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence. About one seventh expressed to have been in detention (detention facility and prison).

A little less than one third received a rejection at the first instance, whereas none got a rejection at the second instance and the decision for about one in seven was still pending. In Greece. A little less than two in three reported that their general experience with the engagement with national authorities/actors while seeking protection or status determination was (rather) not supportive. Furthermore, the Greek material indicated that a little more than two in five regarded the general experience of their engagement with NGOs regarding seeking protection as (rather) not supportive.

In Greece, about two thirds of the interviewees stayed in decentralised accommodation. Two in five of the interviewees reported perceived tensions with security personnel. The majority stated they had received basic healthcare. Two in five declared having received childcare support. A little more than three in four answered they had attended a language class. Also, slightly fewer than two in five claimed to have attended a vocational course or training. Regarding the experience with reception administrators, about two in five reported that they perceived this as (rather) supportive.

One in four could choose their own housing/facility in Greece. A little less than three in four reported to be satisfied with the region they are living in. A little less than two in five of the respondents answered they were working to earn money and one in nine experienced some kind of discrimination in the labour market. Almost all respondents declared they had experienced a very difficult situation, such as a serious accident, natural catastrophe, rape, war, abuse, torture. Slightly more than half of the interviewees expressed psychological ill-health at the time of the interview. Also, a little less than two in five expressed physical ill-health. Close to four out of five characterised their relationships with their neighbours in Greece as close and friendly.

3.5 Italy

3.5.1. National level of healthcare - Macro system

The Italian country report on health (Ibrido & Marchese, 2020) indicates that Italy is inclusive towards migrants in their access and right to health care. This is achieved through extensive legislature made up of various Articles, Court Decisions and Cassations.³ The basis of

³ Cassation is the highest and last judicial remedy in the country.

migrants' right to this healthcare resides in Article 32 of the Italian Constitution, which states, "The Republic safeguards health as a fundamental right of the individual and as a collective interest and guarantees free medical care to the indigent". The Constitutional Court clarifies the essential core of the right to health should encompass migrants too (ex multis, Decisions nos. 252/2001, 432/2005 306/2008 (Ibrido & Marchese, 2020, 45)).⁴ However, it must be said that these extensive legislations at the macro level do not always translate adequately into the micro level.

3.5.2. Institutional level of healthcare - Meso system

In Italy, serious mental and psychosocial problems are not uncommon among asylum seekers and refugees. While most asylum seekers and refugees do suffer negative psychological conditions, migrants in general show better health conditions than Italians in the period immediately after their arrival in Italy, though there are disparities in the overall health (Southeast Asians from India, Pakistan and Bangladesh rank the highest in terms of health, while North African women were the most disadvantaged) (Ibrido & Marchese, 2020). Some migrants were victims of torture and inhuman or degrading treatment during their journey or in detention camps, and may have been subjected to forced labour.

Sometimes I feel sick, and I go to hospital, but it is more psychological, good health physically, but mentally I don't think so, but I'm not seeing a doctor. I'm depressed, I'm not getting assistance for this, even if I told them about it. (Young migrants from Nigeria, Ghana and Libya, in Ibrido & Marchese, 2020)

The interviewees also reported symptoms potentially compatible with the so-called "exhausted migrant effect" and insomnia (Ibrido & Marchese, 2020).

3.5.3. Individual psychosocial health - Micro system

In Italy, most of the interviewees were Muslim, though a significant number were Christian. The variances in religious beliefs did not result in any problems and while religion itself and religious belief did not impact on psychological wellbeing in migration and integration, it is worthy to note that the reception and integration activities carried out by religious institutions did impact on wellbeing as some religious institutions provide protection from xenophobia and through provision of their humanitarian activities. In particular, the interviewee, who works in a centre of first reception, declares:

We don't go to churches with Muslims, however there are Muslim groups, as in Lamezia Terme, that invite our kids to celebrate the feast of the sacrifice in September together with them. In our centre we invited other Muslim boys and they had a party with the Catholics. (Ibrido & Marchese, 2020)

No relevant psychological impact of religious beliefs on the migration and integration processes emerges from the interviews. However, it is important to note the importance of the reception and integration activities carried out by religious institutions.

An important role is played by religious institutions, especially in Italy. If there has not been a drift towards xenophobia, this is largely due to the religious institutions that

⁴About the constitutional right to health, see, ex multis, Morana 2018.

have tried to maintain a certain position towards the phenomenon. Humanitarian corridors, [...] are basically managed by religious organisations such as the Community of Sant'Egidio and the Waldesian church. It means that they are able to provide necessary facilities for people who need protection. (Ibrido & Marchese, 2020)

Some interviewees also argue that the role of the Church was of a major importance in the process of integration in the new country.

If I had to indicate an actor, without making a distinction between Catholic and non-Catholic organisations, I must say that the religious world in general has played a fundamental role, even the Pope himself. The first visit of the Pope was to Lampedusa, this symbolism is important. (Ibrido & Marchese, 2020, p.48)

3.5.4. Social and psychological determinants

The quantitized Italian interview material (Cetrez & Barthoma, 2020) showed that approximately two in three received a rejection at the first instance and the decision for a rejection at the second instance was pending for almost all. As for the Italian case, a little less than two in five claimed that their general experience with the engagement with national authorities/actors to seek protection or status determination was (rather) not supportive. Furthermore, none expressed their experience of the engagement with NGOs regarding seeking protection as (rather) not supportive.

None of the interviewees expressed perceived tensions with security personnel. Also, all of the interviewees declared they had received basic healthcare. Almost all interviewees claimed having attended a language class. Half of the participants attended a vocational course or training.

The minority (about one in ten) could choose their own housing/facility in Italy. All of the respondents were satisfied with the region they are living in. Slightly less than one in five specified to be working to earn money. All of the respondents indicated they had experienced a very difficult situation, e.g. a serious accident, natural catastrophe, rape, war, abuse, torture. Slightly more than one in five expressed psychological ill-health at the time of the interview. Slightly less than one in three expressed physical ill-health. All of the respondents in Italy characterised their relationships with their neighbours in Italy as close and friendly.

3.6 Austria

3.6.1. National level of healthcare - Macro system

From the Austrian country report (Josipovic & Reeger, 2020) it is possible to underline that in Austria, there is a recognition of refugees' and asylum seekers' right of free access to the healthcare system. A submission of an asylum application, grants applicants basic medical care and basic dental treatment. Once granted recognition as a refugee, basic care is upgraded to the insurance of a standard insurance card (e-card) and they become part of the insurance system as Austrian citizens (Josipovic & Reegar, 2020, 46). Persons under subsidiary protection do not receive an e-card unless employed in Austria. Otherwise, they

receive health care through a health insurance voucher that enables them to use services such as examinations and treatment. While asylum seekers are automatically exempt from prescription fees, recognised refugees can apply for exemption from prescription fees if their monthly income is below a certain limit.

3.6.2. Institutional level of healthcare - Meso system

From the country report (Josipovic & Reeger, 2020) it appears that language and bureaucratic barriers are some of the major complication factors that may limit newcomers to seek medical and psychological help.

In principle, the care is there, all refugees are entitled to medical care. Of course, there are problems for the individual when he/she goes to the doctor, dares to express things, because he/she doesn't know German well yet, even in hospital. [...] They actually need mediators to help them.... because languages are a problem. (Expert working in public administration in Vienna, Josipovic & Reeger, 2020)

Experts also argue that individuals are confronted with traumatising events that occurred in the country of origin or on their way to Austria. In this phase of "exhaling", trauma reappears and must be dealt with. They also highlight that traumatising can be hidden in children and the youth, and this is heavily underestimated. Traumatization might be reinforced by the asylum procedure as such and through its long duration.

3.6.3. Individual psychosocial health - Micro system

In the Austrian country report (Josipovic & Reeger, 2020) it became evident that religion is a sensitive topic, because it is related to experiences of persecution and violence in the country of origin but also because many interlocutors were aware of the fact that religion is a central field of conflict concerning the integration of immigrants in Austria. Overall, many of our interlocutors highly value being free from religious norms in a liberal democratic society. However, some of them still experienced discrimination in Austria due to their Muslim faith.

Yes, for me Austria is really a great country, [...] my dream country. [...] [However,] (w)hen I go to AMS [Public Employment Service], people they don't think about me, what can I do or what do I think, they just think 'ah you are Muslim, your wife has a headscarf, why do you pray, do you have Ramadan?' No please, I'm human, not only Muslim. It really bothers me (R09, Josipovic et al. 2020)

For some respondents, thinking about their country of origin and the people they had to leave there is a source of stress and depression (Josipovic et al. 2020). This may be related to the fact that they had imagined their life in Europe to be much easier and that they had assessed their chances of family reunification much too smoothly. For example, children are considered to be an important meaning-making component in the life of migrants. They are seen as a source of hope and motivation. Because many interview partners consider their own position as quite critical and difficult, they project all their hopes and dreams for a better life on their children.

3.6.4. Social and psychological determinants

The quantitized Austrian interview material (Cetrez & Barthoma, 2020) showed that a very small number reported having been tortured at the border and stated having been raped and/or experienced other serious forms psychological, physical or sexual violence.

Slightly more than half got a rejection at the first instance, whereas rejection at the second instance was still pending for approximately nine in ten. As for the Austrian case, a little less than half reported that their general experience of engagement with national authorities/actors to seek protection or status determination was (rather) not supportive. Also, a little more than two in five reported their general experience of the engagement with NGOs regarding seeking protection had been (rather) not supportive.

A little less than half of the interviewees stayed in decentralised accommodation. None of the interviewees expressed perceived tensions with security personnel. The majority (a little more than nine in ten) reported having received basic healthcare. All of the respondents claimed to have received childcare support. Almost all declared they had attended a language class. About one in five attended a vocational course or training. In Austria, one in three answered that their general experience with reception administrators was (rather) supportive.

Slightly more than half of the respondents reported that they could choose their own housing/facility in Austria. The satisfaction and the dissatisfaction of the respondents with the region they are currently living in was about half-half, with slightly more specifying they were satisfied. About one in four reported to be working to earn money in Austria and slightly more than one in three experienced some sort of discrimination in the labour market. A little more than two in five of the respondents indicated they had experienced a very difficult situation, such as a serious accident, natural catastrophe, rape, war, abuse, torture. More than half of the interviewees expressed psychological ill-health at the time of the interview. A little less than half expressed physical ill-health. The Austrian material illustrates that more than three in four of the interview partners expressed an ability to show resilience or to cope. Slightly less than three in four characterised their relationships with their neighbours in Austria as close and friendly.

3.7 Germany

3.7.1. National level of healthcare - Macro system

In the German report (Chemin & Nagel, 2020) it is clear that it is mandatory to have health insurance in the country. There are two types of insurance in Germany: a state health insurance and a private health insurance, whereas both types work through contributions of employers and employees. At the macro level, According to Section 4 AsylbG, asylum seekers are entitled to medical care in the case of acute illness and pain; pregnancy and women in childbirth are included in this definition. However, Section 6 AsylbG states that case-by-case decisions can be made when required by the individual medical conditions. Once their asylum application has been granted or after 15 months after arrival, asylum seekers are eligible for full health services (just like German welfare recipients).

3.7.2. Institutional level of healthcare - Meso system

Germany experienced limitations in terms of mental health care provision (Chemin & Nagel, 2020). Many refugees manifested PTSD symptoms or instances of depression and other mental disorders such as anxiety and panic attacks, however only very few have sought professional help. The causes are financial worries, such as not being able to pay for rent or food, but also language barriers. Many interviewees have expressed concerns with their ability to cope with not only what they had gone through before arriving in Germany, but more pressingly, what they have to endure once they cross the German border and seek asylum.

In general, newcomers have been positive about the role of local faith-based (and secular) volunteers and organizations (Chemin & Nagel, 2020). Religious communities, both Christian and Muslim, as well as private volunteers and volunteers' associations, secular or religiously oriented, are making a positive impact on the lives of refugees in the country. Many others use the openness of some religious institutions to try to feel more integrated. It is important to underline that the role of such opportunities for exchange and dialogue, for sharing common interests, usually produce important connections between guest and host communities.

Finally, some of the newcomers highlighted how impactful negative experiences with clerks and officers dealing with asylum cases can be mentally. Refugees we have interviewed have reported many forms of personal abuses against them, verbal aggressions and attitudes that deepen an already difficult psychological context formed by insecurity, self-doubt and a sense of worthlessness that is typical of individuals going through depression and other forms of mental illness. All this affects integration in various levels. For example, it affects the perception of locals vis-à-vis asylum seekers.

3.7.3. Individual psychosocial health - Micro system

Some interviewees underlined their coping mechanism to deal with problems such as writing, listening to music and the like, while others felt victims of circumstances beyond their control. These issues were exacerbated by conflicts between refugees inhabiting the same camp or even the same room, and the result is more psychological hardship.

[...] When I came here, I felt very bad, but I could handle it myself...Nothing made me happy or sad. In time, I talked to myself, listened to music, read, wrote. I wrote about everything... so I felt better. But I didn't talk to anyone about it. When I came here, I realised I had a problem, I got a feeling like depression... But slowly I was able to deal with it (IRAQ-M-BER2-0208, Chemin & Nagel, 2020)

Some refugees indicated that religion was an important part of overcoming the hurdles imposed on them by the German asylum system or by the very act of fleeing their countries of origin in the first place. For instance, a man in his mid-fifties from Lybia, although clearly a religious person, a practicing Muslim, did not attribute his capacity to overcome his troubles to his religious belief. Instead of religious coping mechanisms, many interviewees referred to the family as a source of consolation or to the wellbeing of their children as a source of motivation to move forward. In most of the experiences religion is envisaged as an impediment rather than a means of personal flourishing. For example, a Syrian woman

attending university in Göttingen felt her clothes made her stand out, attracting unwanted negative attention.

I was the only foreigner in class. I felt unaccepted especially that I have the hijab. They had a different perception regarding me and they were not even talking to me. [...] The only pressure I have other than my studies, is the way I look (SYR-W-LSAX-0812, Chemin & Nagel, 2020)

3.7.4. Social and psychological determinants

The quantitized German interview material (Cetrez & Barthoma, 2020) showed that approximately one twelfth reported to have experienced torture and five out of seventy-seven experienced rape and other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence. About one seventh stated having been arrested at the border and almost one tenth reported detention at the border, whereas approximately one seventh experienced violence at the border. About one eighth reported detention in a detention facility, prison or “other”.

Slightly less than half received a rejection at the first instance, whereas about one in four got a rejection at the second instance and the decision for about one in three was still pending. As in the German (???) case, about one in four mentioned that their general experience of the engagement with national authorities/actors while seeking protection or status determination was (rather) not supportive. A very small number identified the general experience of the engagement with NGOs regarding seeking protection as (rather) not supportive.

In Germany, the majority (three in four) stayed in decentralised accommodation. Slightly more than one in five reported perceived tensions with security personnel. Almost all of the interviewees in Germany declared they had received basic healthcare. Slightly more than two in five reported having received childcare support. About six in seven responded to having attended a language class. Slightly more than two in five attended a vocational course or training. The majority of the respondents (about four in five) claimed that their general experience with reception administrators was (rather) supportive. Slightly less than half of the respondents claimed that they could choose their own housing/facility in Germany. The majority (about six in seven) reported being satisfied with the region they are living in. About two in five of the interviewees were working to earn money and a bit more than one in three experienced some sort of discrimination in the labour market. Slightly more than four in five experienced a very difficult situation, such as a serious accident, natural catastrophe, rape, war, abuse, torture. Slightly more than two in three expressed psychological ill-health at the time of the interview and about one third expressed physical ill-health. Also, the majority of respondents (nine in ten) expressed an ability to show resilience or to cope. Slightly less than three in four characterised their relationships with their neighbours in Germany as close and friendly.

3.8 Turkey

3.8.1. National level of healthcare - Macro system

In the Turkish country report (Rottmann, 2020, referring to Kaya, 2020a, 44) it was underlined that migrants who do not have any health insurance coverage nor the means to

pay for healthcare services will be covered by the General Health Insurance scheme under Turkey's public social security scheme. According to the Temporary Protection Regulation, [Syrians access to health care services is only possible in the province where they are registered (Rottman, 2020)]. Emergency medical services are also provided to non-registered persons. Syrians have the right to access free of charge health care services provided by public health institutions, for both primary and secondary care. Other than primary health care services and public hospitals, Syrians can also approach one of many Migrant Health Centres, located in the provinces with high refugee population density (Kaya, 2020a, 58-59; Rottman, 2020).

3.8.2. Institutional level of healthcare - Meso system

Health services are the Turkish government service provision area that migrants speak about most positively (Rottmann, 2020). However, despite migrants' laudable legal access to treatment, interviews indicate that they still face difficulties accessing services in practice. Bureaucratic and linguistic barriers are the hardest to overcome. Migrants not owning an ID card might find restrictions in accessing medical services in the country. In addition, the lack of Turkish language ability and translators is one major problem, causing some migrants with means to seek treatment at private hospitals or Syrian health centres, which charge fees. Studies have also found out that differences in culture may also lead refugee patients to "complain that they were unable to understand the diagnosis properly or do not trust the diagnosis". (Cloeters & Osseiran, 2019, 16)

The medical complaints that newcomers denounce are also seen to be a source of physical distress.

Yes, I was having a health issue in my neck from Syria and still until now. Maybe it is because of the house work, or psychological effects. I went to the hospital and had it checked. They said that I am good, but they gave me an appointment to check again. So, I will see later. (Interview, Istanbul, 2018, OzU_5, Rottmann, 2020)

Some migrants find life in Turkey to be very stressful, feeling an overwhelming financial as well as social pressure, both in terms of finding a job and the latter in terms of feeling not welcomed by locals and having a negative impact on their psychological well-being (Rottmann, 2020). These, especially financial pressures, can, in turn, lead to strained family relationships which then add to already existing psychological distress. In this regard, loss and disappointment as well as the sheer geographical distance between family members and their own ways of coping with migration and the stress and pressures that accompany this, have been mentioned as factors which strain family bonds.

Due to the financial problems and lack of a proper job fitting to my qualifications, we are under stress here. My wife and I are fighting a lot. Although we married for love, we are just living.... If there was no psychological and financial pressure, it would be better. Compared to other Arab countries, our conditions are still better. Also, compared to conditions within Syria, we are doing better (Interview, Şanlıurfa, 2018, SR11_6, Rottmann, 2020).

These interviews indicate, according to Rottmann (2020) that most migrants would certainly agree with this man that their situation is better in Turkey, than it would be in other Arab countries, but feelings about Europe are more mixed, with some viewing onward travel positively and others feeling more permanently settled.

One point that emerges often in the Turkish interviews is that language learning has been therapeutic and a great aid to forming social relations with Turks, which eases psychological stress.

[...] I was in a students' dormitory, and I was the only Arabic speaker. I didn't know Turkish at all. I was feeling very lonely. Then, when I started to learn Turkish, it was better. I started communicating with people. Nowadays, there is no time to think about depression (laughing) (Interview, Istanbul, 2018, OzU_20, Rottmann, 2020).

3.8.3. Individual psychosocial health - Micro system

According to the Turkish country report, friends and family have been mentioned as important (psychological) support systems (Rottmann, 2020). Children are especially identified as a source of joy and hope. Other resources in terms of meaning-making are inner strength, maintaining a positive outlook for the future as well as religious beliefs that can be supportive and give hope. Moreover, language learning has been mentioned as a therapeutic way to connect and integrate. Migration can strengthen religious beliefs and practices such as going to the mosque and visiting religious services more frequently. A feeling of connectedness with locals due to a shared religion has also been mentioned as part of a system of support.

Overall, Syrian families are under tremendous financial and social pressure. When asked about their coping strategies, many people mention having no strategies or no one who supports them (Rottmann, 2020). Some others find their strength in self-motivation, religion and ties with family and friends. Some people directly mention receiving psychological support from friends and family.

I love my husband. He loves me. When he sees that I'm sad he comes right away and cares. I support him the same way. I never needed psychological support (Interview, Izmir, 2018, SR11_16, Rottmann, 2020).

At night when I go to my house, if they are awake, my daughters welcome me and do good things for me. So I forget all the tired moments, and I forget my worries. (Interview, Istanbul, 2018, OzU_16, Rottmann, 2020).

For almost all of our interviewees, religious and cultural resources for coping are very much based in Islam. An interviewee explained the important role of saying prayers.

I felt psychologically distressed. I'm not used to leaving my family, my country and all of my relatives in Syria. I came here for the first time I went out like that. We all weren't expecting to go out like that, for example to Turkey or to Istanbul.

The interviewer asked: what did you do when you had such a feeling? Did you go to someone?

He responded, 'I go to the mosque and pray. I pray to my God' (Interview, Istanbul, 2018, Bilgi_16, Rottmann, 2020).

Migration was also seen as strengthening religious belief and practice. Some respondents described becoming more religious in Turkey. Even those who haven't become more

religious often described a feeling of closeness with Turks due to being Muslim and living with Muslim neighbours.

3.8.4. Social and psychological determinants

The quantitized Turkish interview material (Cetrez & Barthoma, 2020) showed that very few reported they suffered from a serious illness and again very few reported being elderly. In addition, a small number reported to have experienced rape and other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence. Furthermore, very few reported being held in detention in either detention facilities or “other”.

None of the respondents received a rejection for the first instance, whereas for rejection at the second instance the decision for half of them was still pending. Deriving from the Turkish material, a little more than one in four declared that their general experience with the engagement with national authorities/actors while seeking protection or status determination was (rather) not supportive. Furthermore, the Turkish material shows that a little more than one in four assessed the general experience with the engagement with NGOs regarding seeking protection as (rather) not supportive.

In Turkey, a little more than half of the interviewees stayed in decentralised accommodation. Moreover, a few reported perceived tensions with security personnel. Six in seven declared have received basic healthcare. Slightly less than one in four stated they had received childcare support. About two in five claimed to have attended a language class and one in ten attended a vocational course or training. Slightly more than two thirds of the respondents declared that their general experience with reception administrators was (rather) supportive.

Almost the totality of respondents in Turkey could choose their own housing/facility. Slightly more than three in four of the respondents said they were satisfied with the region they are currently living in. More than half of the interviewees replied that they were working to earn money and more than half experienced some kind of discrimination in the labour market. Slightly less than half of the respondents declared they experienced a very difficult situation, such as a serious accident, natural catastrophe, rape, war, abuse, torture. Psychological ill-health was indicated by slightly more than one in five of the respondents in Turkey and slightly less than one in four indicated physical ill-health. Two in three of the interview partners expressed an ability to show resilience or to cope. Approximately two in three characterised their relationships with their neighbours in Turkey as close and friendly.

3.9 Iraq

3.9.1. National level of healthcare - Macro system

Iraq's country report (Warda et al. 2020) highlighted that current healthcare does not rest on the legislature, but rather on an interlaced effort system with contributions from the government, Non-governmental Organisations, and International Organisations like WHO and UNICEF. This model is due to the structural issues that Iraq has faced on account of sanctions, civil conflict and wars. Thus provision of healthcare for asylum seekers and refugees are relegated to the meso level.

3.9.2. Institutional level of healthcare - Meso system

According to the Iraqi country report (Warda et al. 2020) the living conditions of the new refugees were poor. The families live mostly in overcrowded primitive housing, lacking sanitary infrastructure, and are exposed to harsh weather conditions, which may increase the spread of skin and respiratory diseases. Some refugees complained about the lack of medicines, treatments and medical assistance. A Syrian female refugee said "I go to a clinic for treatment and no one helps me. There are not enough medicines in the clinic" (Irq-16SHMB-Micro-Syr-F-No.16, Warda et al. 2020).

Most of the refugees also suffer from trauma and psychological stress due to the events that occurred in their home country in addition to the current living conditions.

My asylum in Iraq affected me physically, as I have been sick to date and because of the difficult circumstances I have lived in, I have also been psychologically affected a lot, I get depression episodes. So, I go to my neighbours to relieve that. Living in Iraq brings psychological pressures on me. The social life has led to psychological pressure on me because I have children and there is no work for my husband. These circumstances put a lot of pressure on me when I find my children without schools and I cannot meet their demands (Irq-18MYA-Micro-Syr- F-No.18, Warda et al. 2020).

Some refugees complained about the lack of assistance from humanitarians organisations:

I asked for medical assistance from humanitarian organisations, no one met my request, as I requested treatment, medicine and surgery, but my request was rejected when I submitted this in writing (Irq-18MYA-Micro-Syr-F-No.18, Warda et al. 2020).

While other refugees confirmed to the field team that they received medical attention, stressing that first aid accompanied them after entering Iraq, and that civil society organisations provided them with medical assistance.

After we entered Iraq, they provided us with medical assistance with food and services, and received assistance from foreign organizations (Irq-8APA- Micro-Syr-M-No.8, Warda et al. 2020)

3.9.3. Individual psychosocial health - Micro system

When it comes to religion and faith they played an important role in the refugees overcoming the difficulties they went through. This aspect was a factor of patience and out of the impact of the shocks of many Syrian refugees and contributed greatly to their integration. In the same context, the relations between family members, close relatives or children played a role in giving an existential incentive to the refugees, which gave a stronger meaning to the continuation of their lives and their integration in the new society.

3.9.4. Social and psychological determinants

The quantitized Iraqi interview material (Cetrez & Barthoma, 2020) showed that slightly less than one tenth reported detention at the border. Approximately one in twenty reported detention in detention facilities or "other".

A very small number of respondents received a rejection at the first instance whereas none got a rejection at the second instance. As for the Iraqi cases, a little more than one in ten reported that their general experience with the engagement with national authorities/actors when seeking protection or status determination was (rather) not supportive. Moreover, the quantitized Iraqi interview material indicates that a little more than one in three reported the general experience of the engagement with NGOs regarding seeking protection as (rather) not supportive.

In Iraq, the majority (two-thirds) of the interviewees stayed in decentralised accommodation. In addition, a very small number reported perceived tensions with security personnel. Slightly less than two in five expressed have received basic healthcare. Slightly more than one in four of the respondents declared to have received childcare support. Almost none of the respondents answered they had attended a language class. Slightly more than one in four attended a vocational course or training in Iraq. The vast majority declared that their experience with reception administrators was (rather) supportive.

Slightly less than half of the respondents declared they could choose their own housing/facility in Iraq. Slightly more than three in five claimed they are satisfied with the region they are living in. Furthermore, about three in five of the interview partners in Iraq claimed to be working to earn money and slightly less than one in five experienced some sort of discrimination in the labour market. Most of the participants (about eight of nine) experienced psychological ill-health. Furthermore, more than half of the interview partners in Iraq experienced physical ill-health. Additionally, slightly more than half expressed an ability to show resilience or to cope. A little less than three in four characterised their relationships with their neighbours in Iraq as close and friendly.

3.10 Hungary

3.10.1. National level of healthcare - Macro system

From Hungary's country report (Gyollai et al. 2020) it was possible to understand that the government of Hungary adopts a strong anti-immigrant position. This hostility towards migrants gives rise to minimal policies towards migrants, outside of being a transit country. Access to healthcare is marred with a reluctance at a macro level to enact policies receptive to the healthcare needs of migrants.

3.10.2. Institutional level of healthcare - Meso system

It was underlined that screening and treatment of asylum seekers' mental health is insufficient, if not lacking altogether. In addition, in order to see a doctor, consult their lawyers or be interviewed, asylum seekers in transit zones, including women and children, had to be escorted by armed police. This is perceived as intimidating behaviour by the newcomers as some of the micro-level interviews highlighted.

I mean, this whole impression makes you scared, because when you're going for the interviews, you pass policemen around this room and when you enter that room, I mean, there used to be a policeman again, waiting for you here to come out. (Gyollai et al. 2020)

Moreover, the capacity of medical units in the zones is 10 persons respectively. While general practitioners are available daily, children's doctors are only available twice a week. Whenever specialist care is necessary, asylum seekers are taken to medical institutions in the vicinity of the zones in prisoner transport vans.

The assessment of vulnerable groups in special need, including LGBTI groups, their appropriate treatment, accommodation, and the training of staff in this regard is lacking altogether. No adequate support is provided for victims of domestic-, sexual- or gender based abuse.

According to one of the meso-level respondents, asylum seekers mainly received canned food, they had no access to a diverse or healthy diet unless social workers provided them with some vegetables and fruit. Deprivation of food for asylum seekers in transit zones has become a standard procedure that has also been denounced by the UNHCR.

The role of government is also of primary importance in the reception process for newcomers. The asylum seekers we have interviewed corroborated the accounts of public intolerance, and explained how difficult it is for them to socialise with locals due to the government's anti-immigrant stance and campaigns:

Actually, before it wasn't affecting us too much, but it all came when the government started like... Doing this propaganda, saying migrants are bad, asylum seekers want to take away Hungarian jobs... Then, it's all during that time when everything started to change a bit, people's reactions towards us started to change a bit, to shift. Before people were very friendly and then, right now, I could say that some people are drawing that line between us and them. They don't want to be friendly, they see us as a negative influence on people... (HUN12, Gyollai et al. 2020)

In addition, wages paid for refugees are way below average, workplace exploitation is not uncommon. One interviewee mentioned that she has been regularly tasked with physically overwhelming duties outside her job description. Because of language barriers, however, she was unable to raise these issues.

In my working place people show they like you, but they want to use you. My colleagues like kidding with me, but if I do so, they get offended immediately. Every Hungarian has holiday, except us, the Asians, who work in the kitchen. We hardly have a day off and we work a lot. Just look at my hands. [His hands were totally dry. They were overused.] (HUN10, Gyollai et al. 2020)

3.10.3. Social and psychological determinants

The quantitized Hungarian interview material (Cetrez & Barthoma, 2020) showed that approximately one sixth reported to have experienced rape and/or other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence at the border. About two thirds reported to have been arrested at the border. More than one third was detained at the border and one in eight experienced violence at the border. As for the Hungarian cases, slightly less than two thirds were detained in a detention facility.

About one in three received a rejection at the first instance. Furthermore, a little less than half specified that their general experience of engagement with national authorities/actors when seeking protection or status determination was (rather) not supportive. Concerning the

general experience with engagement with NGOs regarding seeking protection, one in eight specified this to have been (rather) not supportive.

In Hungary, all of the respondents stayed in decentralised accommodation. One third reported perceived tensions with security personnel. All of the interview partners in Hungary declared having received basic healthcare. Approximately two in three stated having attended a language class. In addition, the majority specified that their general experience with reception administrators was (rather) supportive.

All of the respondents claimed they could choose their own housing/facility in Hungary. Slightly more than four in five specified they are satisfied with the region they are living in. The majority reported to be working to earn money and all of the respondents stated having experienced some kind of discrimination in the labour market. Two thirds had experienced a very difficult situation, such as a serious accident, natural catastrophe, rape, war, abuse, torture. Slightly more than one in five indicated psychological ill-health and approximately one in three referred to physical ill-health. The majority (six in seven) expressed an ability to show resilience or to cope. Slightly less than half characterised their relationships with their neighbours in Hungary as close and friendly.

3.11. Country and thematic overview

The following overview aims to present the findings first by country, followed by themes identified as central for psychosocial health: determinants, macro and meso level importance and experiences of health, micro level experiences of health, and specific individual coping methods. A final overview by gender and country of origin is also presented.

Table 1. Overview of psychosocial health conditions by country

Country	Social and psychological determinants	Macro and meso systems	Micro system	Coping methods
Sweden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Violence experienced at border: Medium • Asylum rejection: Low • Choice in housing: Medium • Current employment: Medium • Discrimination in labour market: Medium • Exposure to trauma: High • Support from authorities to seek protection: High • Attended a language class: High • Friendly relations with neighbours: Medium • Basic healthcare received: High • Psychological ill-health: High • Physical ill-health: Low • Resilience and coping: High 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of cultural understanding and competency • Lack of interpreters • Perceived discrimination • Language barrier 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender as a limitation to reaching out for psychological assistance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive coping through religion • Negative/ self-destructive religious coping methods • Relying on family and friends • Children as a life motivation
United Kingdom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Violence experienced at border: Low • Asylum rejection: High • Choice in housing: High • Current employment: Medium • Discrimination in labour market: High • Exposure to trauma: High • Support from authorities to seek protection: Medium • Attended a language class: High • Friendly relations with neighbours: Medium • Basic healthcare received: High • Psychological ill-health: High • Physical ill-health: High • Resilience and coping: High 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governmental practices: bureaucratic • Security and safety in the neighbourhood • Lack of understanding about how the NHS works • Confusion about entitlements amongst health workers often prevents refugees receiving free services • Complexity of the rules and confusion surrounding proof of identity documents • Lack of a permanent address to receive correspondence affects access to mental health services • Language barrier • Access to community networks/one's cultural group 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Socio-cultural integration • Prolonged individual asylum decisions • Connections to family, a facilitation of 'hope' • Access to sufficient psychological care and assistance • Isolation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family security and support • Marital intimacy
Poland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Violence experienced at border: Low • Asylum rejection: Medium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religious and ethnic affiliation. • Cultural differences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceived racial discrimination in access to healthcare and in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religion as a positive coping mechanism to

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Choice in housing: High Current employment: Medium Discrimination in labour market: Low Exposure to trauma: High Support from authorities to seek protection: Medium Attended a language class: High Friendly relations with neighbours: Medium Basic healthcare received: High Psychological ill-health: High Physical ill-health: Medium Resilience and coping: High 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Language barrier Lack of specialised healthcare personnel for trauma Organisational and financial deficiencies Racism and Islamophobia Structural challenges of access to healthcare 	the job market	foster integration
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Violence experienced at border: Missing Asylum rejection: Medium Choice in housing: Low Current employment: Medium Discrimination in labour market: Low Exposure to trauma: High Support from authorities to seek protection: Medium Attended a language class: High Friendly relations with neighbours: High Basic healthcare received: High Psychological ill-health: Medium Physical ill-health: Medium Resilience and coping: Missing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Area of residence Residence in a camp/hotspots leads to access to only basic health care. Residence in camps leads to isolation Rural/Urban discrepancies in access to health care Language and communication barrier Structural and operational deficiencies within the health system Inadequate funding for the health system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to healthcare Long waiting times at the hospitals Inhuman or degrading treatment in reception facilities Increase in suicide attempts and self-harm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No mention of coping methods
Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Violence experienced at border: Low Asylum rejection: High Choice in housing: Low Current employment: Low Discrimination in labour market: Missing Exposure to trauma: High Support from authorities to seek protection: Medium Attended a language class: High Friendly relations with neighbours: High Basic healthcare received: High Psychological ill-health: Low Physical ill-health: Low Resilience and coping: Missing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bureaucratic and governmental delays in issuance of insurance cards. Lack of linguistic and intercultural competencies among health personnel Bureaucratic delays in issuing healthcare cards High levels of misperception from citizens Communication with healthcare personnel 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exposure to torture and inhuman or degrading treatment during journey or in reception facilities Forced labour experience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Religious practices

Austria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Violence experienced at border: Low ● Asylum rejection: Medium ● Choice in housing: Medium ● Current employment: Low ● Discrimination in labour market: Medium ● Exposure to trauma: Medium ● Support from authorities to seek protection: Medium ● Attended a language class: High ● Friendly relations with neighbours: High ● Basic healthcare received: High ● Psychological ill-health: Medium ● Physical ill-health: Medium ● Resilience and coping: High 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Language barrier ● Migrants lack knowledge about the structure of the Austrian healthcare system ● Waiting for a final decision on asylum application 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Separation from family members ● Stress related outcome from long asylum procedures ● Trauma (from the country of origin and asylum procedure) related outcomes ● Somatic illnesses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Religion as a positive coping mechanism to adapt in the new country
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Violence experienced at border: Low ● Asylum rejection: Medium ● Choice in housing: Medium ● Current employment: Medium ● Discrimination in labour market: Medium ● Exposure to trauma: High ● Support from authorities to seek protection: High ● Attended a language class: High ● Friendly relations with neighbours: High ● Basic healthcare received: High ● Psychological ill-health: High ● Physical ill-health: Low ● Resilience and coping: High 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Language barrier ● Difficulty navigating complex healthcare structures ● General lack of information about healthcare 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of access for psychological support ● Lack of monetary resources to access psychological support ● Negative experiences with/from healthcare officials ● Legal status: asylum seekers are unable to adequately access healthcare, and the stress that comes with the asylum process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Writing ● Listening to music ● Family as a positive element in the integration process ● Local faith-based (and secular) volunteers and organisations

Turkey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Violence experienced at border: Low • Asylum rejection: (None) • Choice in housing: High • Current employment: Medium • Discrimination in labour market: Medium • Exposure to trauma: Medium • Support from authorities to seek protection: High • Attended a language class: Medium • Friendly relations with neighbours: High • Basic healthcare received: High • Psychological ill-health: Low • Physical ill-health: Low • Resilience and coping: High 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility issues with access to healthcare (ID card issues) • Language barrier: lack of interpreters in most healthcare facilities • Overcrowded hospitals • Discrimination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial pressure • Finding a job • Feeling not welcomed by locals • Problems with access to healthcare due to lack of documents • Mental stress from caring for family members • Psychological stress leading to somatic health crisis, e.g., back pain. • Stress from having chronic illness • Depression and PTSD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family fostering integration and limits feelings of loneliness • Religion as a positive coping mechanism • Cultural associations to foster integration • Friends as a way of integrating and avoiding loneliness • Self-motivation as a positive coping mechanism to avoid depression
Iraq	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Violence experienced at border: Low • Asylum rejection: Low • Choice in housing: Medium • Current employment: Medium • Discrimination in labour market: Low • Exposure to trauma: Missing • Support from authorities to seek protection: High • Attended a language class: Low • Friendly relations with neighbours: High • Basic healthcare received: Medium • Psychological ill-health: High • Physical ill-health: Medium • Resilience and coping: Medium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Region of residence (e.g. camps, urban/rural regions prone to conflict) determine access to healthcare and mental stability • Political, social and economic instability • Strains in the provision of healthcare services • Limited healthcare in proportion to suffering • Lack of coordinated efforts to ensure adequate healthcare services in camps • Provision of only primary healthcare in camps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overcrowded primitive housing • Lack of sanitary infrastructure • Exposure to harsh weather conditions which may increase the spread of dermatological and respiratory diseases • Lack of medicines, treatments and medical assistance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Religion and faith in general as positive coping mechanisms
Hungary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Violence experienced at border: Low • Asylum rejection: Medium • Choice in housing: High • Current employment: High • Discrimination in labour market: High • Exposure to trauma: High 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal status (e.g. asylum seekers endure the harshest challenge in accessing food, and healthcare • Belonging to a social minority, e.g. a member of the LGBTQ+ community • Intolerance, discrimination and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wages paid for refugees are way below average • Workplace exploitation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No mention of coping methods

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Support from authorities to seek protection: Medium ● Attended a language class: High ● Friendly relations with neighbours: Medium ● Basic healthcare received: High ● Psychological ill-health: Low ● Physical ill-health: Low ● Resilience and coping: High 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● exploitation of migrants. ● Strong government anti-immigrant policies. ● Abuse of human rights 		
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Note. The grading (low - 0-30% of responses; medium/average - 31-60% of responses; high - 61-100% of responses) for social determinants is based on the quantitized data, presented in each country profile. It is not intended to give exact figures, but more an indication of how frequent it has been in the interview material.

3.11.1. RESPOND countries

Social determinants in the RESPOND countries can be summarised as follows (for additional information for each country, see also the summative table of health, in Barthoma et al., 2020).

In Sweden, we can underline that the main social determinants in the integration of newcomers are the lack of cultural and language understanding that generate social barriers and perceived discrimination. This can also have a significant impact on health resulting in the lack of or delay in access to health facilities. In this setting, gender is also underlined as a limitation - interestingly only reported in the Swedish material. In some cases, women felt more unsure to ask for help due to the fear of losing custody of their children. Offspring and family, together with positive religious coping, are also the main motivators for newcomers to integrate into the new environment.

In the **United Kingdom** newcomers face mostly bureaucratic limitations, concerning complicated rules about the access to identification system and the National Health system. These are shown to have consequences for the newcomers' health due to delays in governmental practices causing feelings of isolation. In addition, under the individual psychosocial point of view, the prolonged asylum decisions were highlighted to have negative consequences, together with the lack of sociocultural integration and insufficient connections to family members resulting again in feelings of isolation and loneliness. Under the coping mechanisms the most important are family support and security and marital intimacy.

In **Poland**, the social determinants influencing integration are cultural differences and language barriers, resulting in limited access to healthcare facilities. In addition, the healthcare personnel are not sufficiently equipped to deal with trauma related conditions due to organisational and financial deficiencies. In addition, episodes of islamophobia and racism were experienced by newcomers, together with racial discrimination in the job market. Religion and in particular Christianity, was seen as a positive integration mechanism in the new country. However, some episodes of islamophobia were witnessed among Muslim newcomers.

In **Greece** the social determinants are language and communication barriers together with structural societal operational barriers due to inadequate funding. These factors resulted, on the health level, in an increase in depression, episodes of self-harm and suicide also as a result of inhumane treatment in the reception facilities. On the individual psychosocial level the difficulty of accessing the healthcare system was the result of racial discrimination and insufficient funding.

In **Italy** the main social determinants are reported as the lack of linguistic and intercultural competencies, bureaucratic delays in healthcare cards, and misperception of newcomers. The psychosocial factors include inhumane treatment in reception facilities and during the journey and episodes of forced labour. The positive coping mechanisms were identified in religious practices.

In **Austria** the main negative social determinants are again language barriers, lack of knowledge about the healthcare system and long waiting times for final asylum decisions. This leads to stress-related health issues such as trauma and somatic problems. From the psychosocial point of view the separation from family members is the main stressor among newcomers. As a coping mechanism, it is possible to find religious practices again.

In **Germany** the main social determinants for newcomers are language barriers, difficulties navigating the healthcare system and negative experiences with healthcare

officials. These together with lack of monetary resources influence the individual's ability to access healthcare. The main coping mechanisms have been identified as writing, listening to music, family's support and local faith based and/or secular associations.

In **Turkey** the social determinants entail the absence of interpreters in healthcare facilities, overcrowded hospitals and discrimination. The health determinants are characterised by stress related to family and chronic issues. Psychosocially the main limitations result in financial pressure and social pressure in finding housing and jobs together with problems relating to limitations in access to healthcare due to the lack of necessary documents. The main coping elements are the support of family and friends, religious and cultural associations and self-motivation.

In **Iraq** the social determinants have been identified with political, social and economical instability and strains in the healthcare system. Inhumane and degrading housing facilities and the absence of medications are the factors that had the greatest impact on the psychosocial level. Coping was again associated with religion and faith in general.

Hungary is the country that shows the least information about migrants' integration. It was possible to highlight that wages discrimination and workplace exploitation were the factors that had the biggest impact on newcomers' health.

3.11.2. Thematic overview

The empirical material from the different countries will be presented thematically, along the determinants, macro and meso levels, micro level and coping methods.

Regarding **social and psychological determinants**, almost all countries displayed complicated factors such as asylum rejections, border arrests and exposure to trauma in the form of rape, war, torture, serious accidents, natural catastrophe or abuse. Though the extent of these factors was reported to different degrees in the RESPOND countries, it is serious enough to find that these factors were present and thus affecting the newcomers in many negative ways. In addition to these three major determinants, there was the repercussion of suffering from ill health, both mentally and physically. Where possible, the ability to choose housing helps in settling down into their new homes and showing resilience. In countries like Sweden and Hungary, there was a distinct discrimination in accessing the labour market, and this proves to be challenging as many individuals report being breadwinners of some sort. Some countries, like Italy, offer some sort of vocational training, though this is not shared by a lot of countries like Greece, Austria, Turkey, and Germany.

The national and institutional levels of health care, in the majority of countries, are connected with difficulties in accessing healthcare due to lack of understanding of the national healthcare system and lack of proper documentation. In countries like Sweden, Italy, Poland, Germany and Turkey, newcomers experienced racial and religious discrimination in accessing healthcare assistance. In addition, countries like Poland, Greece, Turkey and Iraq struggled with insufficient or inadequate healthcare access due to lack of sufficient funding. Moreover, in countries like Italy, the UK, Austria and Turkey newcomers faced difficulties with the bureaucratic process of acquiring the necessary documentation to access healthcare or the job market. Additionally, respondents reported psychological issues, like isolation in the United Kingdom, and an increase in cases of depression, PTSD, attempted suicide and self-harm in Poland. In addition, other forms of stress related to previous and present trauma were experienced in Austria and Turkey. In the UK and Austria

stress was also connected to long asylum procedures. In particular in Turkey, stress was also seen as causing somatic health crises. In Iraq some health related issues resulted after the inhuman or degrading treatment in reception facilities.

The individual level of psychosocial health in some of the interviews was connected with trauma resulting from inhumane treatment during their journey or in the new country, like in Italy and Iraq. In some other countries the problems were related to structural inefficiencies. Additionally, respondents reported psychological issues, such as isolation in the United Kingdom, and increases in cases of depression, PTSD, attempted suicide and self-harm in Poland. In addition other forms of stress related to previous and present trauma were experienced in Austria and Turkey. In the UK and Austria stress was also connected to lengthy asylum procedures. In particular in Turkey, stress was also seen as causing somatic health crises. In Iraq some health-related issues resulted from inhuman or degrading treatment in reception facilities. In countries like Sweden and the UK it was witnessed that proper access to psychological assistance led to positive psychological outcomes. In other countries, discrimination in the job market was the main negative psychological factor. In Greece, Germany, Turkey and Hungary newcomers experienced wages and workplace discrimination that led to stress related to lack of financial resources and housing.

Coping methods in almost all countries resorted to religious or spiritual levels. Some of the respondents even affirmed that they were not religious in their countries of origin. They started their religious path during migration itself or even after arriving in the new country. For many newcomers family and children still play an important role in meaning-making and they are considered as very important elements. In Turkey, UK and Germany family and marital support were underlined as being fundamental elements in coping with difficulties. Having partners and family members living close by is felt to be a significant help in the integration process in the new country. In Germany and Turkey the presence of friends was pointed out, as well as personal coping mechanisms like writing and listening to music. The process of working on one's own self-esteem was underlined as one of the most important elements to improve confidence and benefitting the process of finding a job and housing in the new country.

3.12. Overview by gender and country of origin

3.12.1. Mental health along gender and country of origin

The quantitized material from RESPOND interviews reveals the mental health both by gender and country of origin. The following tables are taken from Cetrez and Barthoma (2020).

Table 2. Express psychological ill health by gender

	Gender	
	Men	Women
Did not express psychological ill health	155 (54.8%)	76 (40%)
Did express psychological ill health	128 (45.2%)	114 (60%)
Total	283 (100%)	190 (100%)

The results reveal that the majority of women expressed psychological ill-health, while not so among men.

Table 3. Express psychological ill health by country of origin

	Country of Origin		
	Syria	Afghanistan	Iraq
Did not express psychological ill health	164 (61.4%)	14 (30.4%)	7 (12.5%)
Did express psychological ill health	103 (38.6%)	32 (69.6%)	49 (87.5%)
Total	267 (100%)	46 (100%)	56 (100%)

Results show that among Afghani and Iraqis the majority express ill-health, but not so among Syrians.

Table 4. Express ability for resilience, by gender

	Gender	
	Men	Woman
Did not express ability for resilience or coping (such as adapt, handle, bounce back, having resources or similar after illness or hardship.	43 (23.2%)	46 (28.0%)
Did express ability for resilience or coping (such as adapt, handle, bounce back, having resources or similar after illness or hardship.	142 (76.8%)	118 (72%)
Total	185 (100%)	164 (100%)

Results show that a clear majority of both men and women express strong resilience.

Table 5. Express ability for resilience or coping, by country of origin

	Country of Origin		
	Syria	Afghanistan	Iraq
Did not express ability for resilience or coping (such as adapt, handle, bounce back, having resources or similar after illness or hardship.	45 (21.2%)	11 (33.3%)	17 (35.4%)
Did express ability for resilience or coping (such as adapt, handle, bounce back, having resources or similar after illness or hardship.	167 (78.8%)	22 (66.7%)	31 (64.6%)
Total	221(100%)	33 (100%)	48 (100%)

Results show that the majority within each country of origin (Afghani, Syrian, and Iraqi) expresses strong resilience.

3.12.2. Vulnerabilities along gender lines

Embedded within the countries and their profiles are distinctions in vulnerability along gender and country of origin lines. These distinctions are based on the quantitized analyses from each country's interview material (Cetrez & Barthoma, 2020). The participants in all RESPOND countries (n=529) are presented as a group, divided by gender (313 male and 216 female) and country of origin (Afghanistan, Syria, and Iraq - other countries of origin are too small in number and thus not presented individually).

Vulnerability categorised in terms of disability was distributed differently among genders. More men (6) than women (1) responded they had a disability. Serious illness was mentioned by 12 men and 12 women and old age was identified for 7 men and 6 women. 8 women mentioned pregnancy. Being a single parent with a minor, was mentioned by 1 man as opposed to 25 women.

Trafficking was mentioned by 2 men and 1 woman. Furthermore, 23 men and 4 women experienced torture. That being said, 18 men and 18 women had experienced rape or some form of physical, psychological and sexual violence.

Vulnerability in terms of being **arrested** at the border was reported by 21 men and 6 women, while being detained was reported by 15 men and 9 women. In addition to **detention** at the border, of the men, 27 were detained in detention facilities, 4 in prison and 3 in other facilities, as opposed to 7 women detained in detention facilities, 3 in prison and 6 in other facilities. Violence experienced at the border along gender lines was experienced by 21 men and 19 women. Gender-based violence was also experienced, by 1 man and 6 women.

Vulnerabilities along **gender lines** when generalised skew in favour of men, owing to the discrepancy in the total sample size. Thus, at face value, men seem to be more vulnerable, except in the areas of pregnancy and childbearing. In this regard, women were made more vulnerable due to pregnancies and making the migratory journey accompanied by a minor. The only vulnerability that both men and women shared equally was the vulnerability of rape or some form of physical, psychological or sexual assault. Yet, this vulnerability when expressed and analysed within the parameters of the differences in total, shows that vulnerability is faced more by women.

3.12.3. Vulnerability based on country of origin

The prevalence of vulnerabilities based on country of origin was conducted among Syrians (292), Afghanis (56), and Iraqis (59). From these totals, the presence of **disabilities** was categorised among 2 Syrians, 0 Afghans and 3 Iraqis. Vulnerability, in terms of being **elderly**, was found among 9 Syrians, 1 Afghan and 2 Iraqis. Also, 15 Syrians, 2 Afghans and 4 Iraqis reported a serious illness as vulnerability. Furthermore, 5 Syrians, 1 Afghan and 2 Iraqis reported vulnerability in terms of **pregnancy** during the migratory journey. The vulnerability of **travelling with a minor**, was found among 13 Syrians, 1 Afghan and 1 Iraqi.

The threat of **trafficking** was not so prevalent, with only 1 Syrian reporting such a vulnerability. Torture was experienced by 4 Syrians, 6 Afghans and 4 Iraqis. In addition, 10 Syrians, 14 Afghans and 3 Iraqis experienced rape and other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence.

Arrest at the border was reported by 6 Syrians, 7 Afghans and 3 Iraqis. With regard to detention, 9 Syrians, 3 Afghans and 3 Iraqis faced the vulnerability of having been detained at the border. In addition to detention at the border, 8 Syrians were held in **detention facilities** and 4 in **prisons**; for Afghans, 8 were detained in facilities and none in prison; similar to Iraqis, where 6 were held in detention facilities and none in prison. In addition to detention there was exposure to violence. This was reported by 16 Syrians, 12 Afghans and 4 Iraqis. Gender-based violence was categorised by 1 Syrian, 3 Afghans and 1 Iraqi.

Vulnerabilities based on **country of origin**, show a disadvantage for Afghans, due to the numbers displayed as a representation of the total. For most vulnerabilities (arrests,

detentions, gender based violence, torture, rape, etc), Afghans were more susceptible and more representative in relation to the total number of Afghans (56).

4. Analysis

This chapter will analyse the material presented along individual, institutional and policy levels, using concepts and models from the theoretical chapter. Here we present and discuss whether there are connections between different levels concerning health, psychosocial determinants and coping methods.

4.1. An Ecological Analysis

This chapter will present the connections between resources, migrant environment, general health concerns/challenges and coping methods availed between different systems of responses, using the Social-ecological model (Ungar, 2012).

Table 6. A bio-ecological framework for resilience

	General health concern/challenges	Psychosocial determinants	Coping methods
Individual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Trend of migrants suffering from ill-health (e.g. depression, PTSD) · A general trend of language and communicative challenge across migrants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Personal strengths and weaknesses · Demographic factors: age and parental status. · Biogenetic factors such as a disability or presence of a chronic illness. · Exposure to adversities (violence, trauma) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Religion as a positive coping method (SWE, PO, IT, IR, TR), providing strength and hope. · Religion as a negative coping method by mitigating seeking therapy (SWE). Also a source for apathy, flight from reality and engaging in self-destructive behaviour. · Engaging in activities like writing, listening to music (DE).
Micro	<p>Family:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Worries related to scattered families · Worries about how to satisfy family needs (e.g. paying rent, providing for the family in general) <p>Friends:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Loss during migration · General fear for/uncertainty of wellbeing (e.g. detention situations) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Existence or lack of access to family, community and cultural networks · Lack of access to healthcare, employment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Support system (children, friends, significant others) · Connections to social, cultural and community networks.

<p>Meso</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · General trend of lack of healthcare personnel equipped for dealing with trauma and mental health · Communicative barriers between healthcare givers and patients · Stigmatisation and perceived discrimination from care givers. · Different perceptions of staff gender roles (Sweden). · Religious discrimination among caregivers in Poland. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Legal status of migrant · Public, private or hybrid healthcare system · Convergence or divergence of cultural ties between migrants and host country 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Use of video interpretation (AU) · Use of interpreters and translators to facilitate communication between caregivers and patients.
<p>Macro</p>	<p>Legislation, policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Discrepancy (discrimination) of legislation among migrant groups in access to healthcare. · Lack of healthcare policies in some countries (GR). · Political and social instability (IR). · Anti-immigrant hostility resulting in inconsistent policies (UK). <p>Institutions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · General trend and structural strain on healthcare institutions (SWE, UK) · Structural deficiencies in the provision of healthcare services (GR, IR) · General trend of lack of capacity in addressing mental health · NGOs also facing capacity shortages (PO, GR) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Economic environment. (Financial crisis in GR) · Political instability leading to destruction of infrastructure and fleeing of healthcare personnel (IR). · Political environment and legislature. · General social cohesion referring to party affiliation (conservative/liberal approaches towards migration) · International agreements and membership of international organisations (EU, UN, WHO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Outsourcing of health- care services to NGOs and Civil Societies (e.g. Red Cross in SWE, Doctors without Borders in GR) · Help from international organisations like UNICEF, WHO in badly affected countries like (GR, IR, TR)

4.1.1. System Analysis

The **general health concerns/challenges** and **psychosocial determinants** emphasise the importance of 'environment' and context with regards to the resilience of a migrant. Analytically, these two demonstrate the lack of control or influence of migrants over factors or resources that challenge or determine their health and resilience. Migrants have little to no control on the challenges at the macro system (lack of policies or strains in health institutions) and whatever control exists in the challenges at the meso (discrimination), micro level (loss or death of family) or even individual (trauma), this is minimum. Psychosocial determinants (legal status, gender, chronic illness, etc) as factors that mitigate or enhance the degree of impact of these challenges to migrants' health and resilience again reside outside of the migrants' sphere of influence. Thus, the existence of resources or lack of, must always be negotiated or renegotiated. The capacity or capability of migrants to successfully negotiate or negotiate for these resources become the degree of impact towards health and resilience. Let us now look more closely at the different levels along challenges and determinants in the ecological model.

The individual and micro systems represent migrant's immediate internal and external stimuli- and as the first and second sphere of resources needed for resilience. The individual system, as the base system is layered around the individual and provides a 'context' of personal qualities, ideological commitments and personal coping strategies (Tol et al. in Panter-Brick & Eggerman, 2012, 372). These resources become the epicenter of a migrant's individualised response capacity to dealing with adversity and showing resilience. The general health concerns are categorically more negative with a trend of migrants suffering from mental ill-health manifested in conditions such as depression or PTSD. This general trend of ill-health is exacerbated by an inability to communicate adequately and effectively in line with accessing healthcare. Thus, the degree of impact of ill-health is assessed by the resources the migrants are able to call from within. These individual (internal) resources and capacities such as age, biogenetic factors (disability, chronic illness), prior exposure to adversities (violence, trauma), migrant's own personal strengths and weaknesses all determine the impact of the adverse effects and the ability to be resilient. Thus, coping mechanisms at this stage are personal, with many migrants marshalling the mechanisms and resources that best equip them with dealing with the stressors and adversities of being a migrant. For many, religion arises as a coping mechanism, with positive or negative outcomes. Positive outcomes are attained when religion is able to provide strength and hope and a positive avenue to meaning-making. In its negative outcomes, religion can lead towards feelings of apathy, flight from reality or even engaging in self-destructive behaviour. Yet, coping and meaning-making are not always religion-based, but instead can be engaging in other activities such as writing or listening to music or reading a book. The variances in a resultant positive or coping mechanism in terms of resilience can be attributed to variations in the individual's internal perceptions and capacity to negotiate or even renegotiate their internal abilities and external stimuli.

The micro system becomes the immediate external stimuli and the second layered system consisting of family and friends. As the second layer, it exerts significant impact on the resilience of migrants. The loss of family during the migratory period to death or/and dispersion, worries of adequately seeing to family needs or the general fear and uncertainty of their wellbeing become significant general stimuli of concern for the individual. The existence or lack of access to family, community or even cultural networks become

indicators of the degree of impact of the system on the individual. Having a support system of any kind, in the form of children, spouse and friends is a coping mechanism of migrants.

The meso level is the first external stimulus outside of the migrant's immediate sphere of influence and the third layered system. It includes the interactions between two or more micro systems such as family, school system, support systems and neighbourhood connectedness. Migrants' health concerns in this system revolve around interactions between caregivers and other micro level networks, such as family or community, and whether these interactions are functional or not. Challenges include a general lack of healthcare personnel equipped with dealing with migrants mental health and trauma and communicative barriers with the caregivers. These challenges can be buttressed with stigmatisation and discrimination (including religious) from caregivers. Yet caregivers themselves have to navigate gender perceptions and their ramifications in dispensing care to migrants. The degree of impact of these challenges to migrants' resilience can be diminished or increased by the factors of the migrants' legal status (asylum seeker, refugee, under international protection), the nature of the healthcare system of the host country (public, private or hybrid), and the degree of convergence or divergence of cultural ties between the migrant and host country. The system employs methods of bridging communication barriers between migrants and caregivers through the use of translators and interpreters provided by agencies or even migrants' family and friends.

The macro system entails the religious, political and cultural norms and values. In this setting, the various health legislations and institutions are included. There are various levels of policies and legislation dedicated to migrant health across various countries: with some countries providing the minimum or maximum resources for healthcare. This discrepancy in legislation can be plotted along political dimensions such as anti-immigrant sentiments (Hungary, Poland, UK) or lack thereof. These discrepancies also exist along capacity and capability lines with some countries unable to provide and maintain substantive policies due to economic, political or even social inadequacies (Greece, Iraq). Health institutions (formal/informal) show a general strain of adequately meeting the health needs (somatic, mental) of migrants due to structural, capacity or capability deficiencies. The degree of impact of these strains on this system is influenced by the domestic and international political environment, economic and social in/stability or even adherence to international organisations such as the EU, UN and WHO, as anchors to the provision of a modicum of acceptable treatment to migrants in need.

To conclude, the coping methods analysed are tailored to each system with the aim of maintaining stability or balance. The coping mechanisms employed at the individual and micro systems are aligned with helping migrants, as individuals to mitigate the immediate internal and external stimulus of adversity. And this includes avenues of religion or religiosity, engaging in social activities and a support system of family and friends. At the meso and macro level, the coping methods manage the discrepancy between the situations and the available resources and thus include methods outside the sphere of influence of migrants. The meso level uses the services of translators and interpreters to meet the demands of communication between caregiver and patients. And the macro system employs the informal services of NGOs and civil societies to level out the strains in formal health institutions.

4.2. An ADAPT Analysis

The final part of the analysis will present the connections between different systems of responses, using the ADAPT-model (Silove, 2013). We are here interested in newcomers' adaptive and extreme responses as coping methods.

Table 7. Functional and dysfunctional coping methods through the ADAPT-model

System	Challenge	Adaptive response	Extreme response
Security/Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exposure to adversity (violence, trauma) pre-migration and on journey Exposure to violence and precarious health conditions in camps and hotspots Insecurity due to socio-political crisis in transit countries (e.g. Iraq) Exposure to institutional abuse especially in camps and hotspots Fear and insecurity about the future deriving from the lengthy asylum procedure and deportation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support system (children, friends, significant others) Connections to social, cultural, religious and community networks Adhering to/practising faith and meaning-making Seeking therapy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feelings of depression PTSD, mental health disorders Mental ill-health leading to suicide attempts
Attachment (Bonds/ Networks)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Loss of family during the migratory journey Dispersal of family members around the world Alienation from various facets of life (job, health, education) due to language barriers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grief over lost family members Grief over lost connections in past life Seeking of psychological help to deal with loss and grief Positive coping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feelings of passivity (not meeting or contacting anyone) leading to depression, or even suicide Feelings of isolation with severance from support networks Negative coping
Justice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiences of discrimination due to ethnicity and religion Racism and stigmatisation with effect on jobs, education, legal status and health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feelings of anger over the situation, especially in unbalanced treatment among asylum seekers Channelling of grievances through legal means 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ghettoization, resulting in isolation and separation from the host country
Role/Identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disruption in the (patriarchal) hierarchy in family units Threatening personal roles within the family when not able to provide/care for family/children Negative media portrayal of migrants and their 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women are pursuing new opportunities in jobs, education Assertiveness of independence among women 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Divorces in marriages Increase in conflict among families Adoption of more conservative and polarising cultural values and worldviews

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · culture · Cultural and worldview incompatibility between migrants and host countries · Change in self-perception, challenging self-worth in relation to “social decline”, e.g. working in low-paid jobs for high skilled individuals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · ‘Perceived’ increase in freedom among households · Divorce in dysfunctional marriages 	
Existential meaning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Difficulty in integration and access to better life due to religious beliefs · Islamophobia · Acquiring asylum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Experience of existential doubt and faith · Converting and re-negotiating religious beliefs to adjust or to gain citizenship. Seen especially among younger migrants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Abandonment of existing belief, without replacing with a new one · Increase in apathy, flight from reality · Alienation and separating from the host country · Conversion to a new religious belief, but not being trusted or welcomed

4.2.1. System Level Analysis

In the following, each pillar is described by the challenges, adaptive and extreme responses and finally related to the social and psychological interventions needed for integration purposes.

Security and Safety, the first pillar of the ADAPT model (Silove, 2013), poses the biggest challenge to the lives and integration of migrants. The war has resulted in a real threat to themselves or to their group, with risks for survival and persisting fear. On their journey, they contend with violence, adversity and extreme trauma. On arrival in host countries, this continues with feelings of insecurity and vulnerability. If lucky, the sense of insecurity results from the strife and anxiety of the long asylum procedure and subsequent deportation. In the worst case scenario, migrant respondents recount violence and feeling unsafe in camps and hotspots and instances of institutional abuse. Still though, to these challenges in security, migrants show adaptive responses by finding support in their family, friends, social and community networks. Yet these adaptive responses are sometimes coupled with extreme responses of terror, panic, depression, PTSD and related reactions. In severe cases, the extreme response manifests itself in suicide attempts. Social intervention on this level entails protection, support and education for the individual and family, to increase their sense of security and enable regaining control. Psychological intervention includes trauma counselling with cultural awareness.

Attachment, the second pillar, is closely related to the sense of security. These challenges target and disrupt emotional ties and bonds. This disruption in bonds pertains to separation or loss of family and even friends, to death or dispersion. Migrant respondents expressed adaptive responses in grieving this loss, in terms of positive coping and in cases where the grief has been insurmountable, psychological health through therapy has been sought. Even arousal and separation anxiety is part of the adaptive response. There have also been extreme responses, with prolonged grief and depression, suicidal thoughts and suicide attempts. Social intervention entails reuniting families and restoring social relations, and promoting rituals for social connection. Psychological intervention entails grief counselling.

Justice, the third pillar, entails human rights violations and abuse. For the newcomers it expresses severe challenges, with a prevalence of discriminatory and racist perceptions and behaviours. These experiences of discrimination cut across all facets of life in education, work and even health. In this regard, anger, frustration, caution in trusting and disillusionment are categorised as adaptive responses. Yet in extreme responses, these discriminatory and racist experiences culminate in extreme anger, in feelings of 'otherness', with a sense of alienation and isolation from the wider society and in the long run of seeking justice in an illegal way, where the goal justifies the means. Social intervention should focus on truth and reconciliation, both with oneself and with others. Psychological intervention can focus on anger management.

The role and identity of migrants, the fourth pillar, is also challenged. These challenges often involve a disruption of institutions and structures, but also of the system of life, not seldom patriarchal. It involves a disruption of family roles, which do not function the same way as before due to various factors such as a precarious financial situation, challenged mental health, change of values and different degrees of adaptation. It also includes the often negative portrayal of migrants and their culture through the media, associating

migration with criminality or with societal and economic burdens. The cultural worldview, including their meaning-making system, is devalued, while the norms and values of majority society are set as a goal.

Women seem to be the primary beneficiaries in the disruption of roles and identity, with many making use of these disruptions to enroll in schools, join the labour market, become more independent, or even find the strength to leave a dysfunctional relationship. Additionally, adaptive responses to role uncertainty or disruption in roles and identities have led to a freer atmosphere among family units. That being said, isolation, deviancy, or increase in conflicts and divorces in marriages are some extreme responses. In extreme cases, the disruption in identity triggers a more conservative and polarising view on identity and role, as migrants strive to mitigate the perceived erosion of their identity. A weakened self-image is balanced with an exaggerated and at times unrealistic collective image, or an increase in polarisation, in terms of us and them categories. Social intervention entails training, work and skill development while psychological intervention entails counselling and family therapy.

Existential meaning, the fifth pillar, often neglected in health studies, reflects the challenges of integrating and balancing a person's inner and outer systems in a context of acculturation. This pillar connects to the previous ones. Any change or disruption of the other pillars, will have an effect on this one, and consequently the reverse. This balance is crucial for one's perception of well-being and self-worth. For many, religious rituals and symbols, as well as religious teachings, are coping methods in making sense of suffering, despair or pain. For others, cultural practices or personal objects seem to show significant importance for existential meaning. Thus, undermining or devaluing cultural values and belief systems, has tremendous consequences for one's ability to uphold a balanced level in the wider context of acculturation. Adaptive responses include a considerable existential doubt about one's religious beliefs, with a healthy re-negotiation or adaption of the parameters of certain religious beliefs in order to best integrate into the host society. The resultant hybrid religious identities are more prevalent among younger migrants than adults. However, extreme responses include a complete loss of faith or even alienation from the original community and host country, without an ability to find a new balanced and integrating worldview system. Social intervention on this level entails religious or political expression and psychological intervention is best provided through humanistic and existential therapy.

4.2.2. Response Analysis: Adaptive or Extreme

The **systems** and the **challenges** accrued to them include affectations and manifestations similar to social and psychosocial health determinants which include work, labour, education, meaning-making and mental health. These challenges are similar in that they reside outside the realm of control of the migrants and as such migrants cannot easily fix them or even avoid them entirely. This inability to actively control the challenges ultimately affects the responses that are shown.

4.2.2.1. Adaptive responses

Presenting adaptive responses relies on the migrant being able to call upon a modicum of resources such as having a support system (family, friends, community networks). Such a support system allows migrants to feel more secure, hold on to bonds, form new or hybrid identities and reorient their sense of self and belonging. In cases where an external support system is not available, other resources such as access to a job, education, housing, health

and a good chance of obtaining refugee status help to present adaptive responses. Adaptive responses are contextual in time and place, which indicates that what may seem functional or working for the individual or group during a specific period, may not be so from the outside or vice versa. Furthermore, resilience is dependent on a group's ability to access available resources for well-being, as well as effectively participate in the social discourse that defines which resources are meaningful (Ungar, 2012). Newcomers feel more comfort staying within their own group for support (Simich & Andermann, 2014) for reasons of language, connections and trust. This may also include support in health promotion, such as seeking a private physician or dentist within the community. A positive atmosphere found within a community and a specific place, can have positive effects on people's psychosocial health. Thus, resilience components, such as family and community, are linked to belief systems (e.g., religion, or ideologies around gender roles), organisational patterns (e.g., family-centred economy) and communication processes (e.g., family storytelling) (Walsh, 2003, in Ungar, 2012). The initial criticism of resilience research, raised in this report, with its emphasis on individual resilience, points to the complexity and diversity of adaptive responses, as well as the normative dimension of what is functional or not, or what is adaptive or not.

Based on the three processes of recovery, sustainability, and growth, presented by Murray and Zautra (in Ungar, 2012), our data shows the following:

- **Recovery:** suggests that people are able to make the necessary psychophysiological and social adjustments in order to return to a level of functioning. Many of the participants in our study had lost significant others and belongings, as well as been exposed to the severe consequences of war. Despite these losses, many of them were able to adjust and rebuild social relations and social networks, as well as find support, such as through local networks, community networks or religious networks.
- **Sustainability:** refers to the ability to sustain one's sense of purpose and engagement in valued social relationships in the face of adversity and the ability to preserve and continue forward with a limited sign of the impact of the stressor. The most clear examples of sustainability are the expression of hope, goals, confidence and agency by participants. Hope and agency, both at individual and collective levels, are the main driving forces for resilience and explain how newcomers tackle the hardships they have left behind and the ones they are facing during integration. A Syrian woman from our study expresses this in terms of self-fulfilment in this way: "I faced a very hard situation and despite all of that I successfully proved myself and stood on my feet with my work, independence, and language." (Syrian woman, Age group 27-50, No.12, in Cetrez, et al., 2020)
- **Growth:** includes the additional gains and advancement following adversity, such as gaining new skills, enhancing self-esteem or providing a new meaningful direction in life. An example is a young mother who would earlier find herself as a bird in a cage, trapped and unable to fly out, to free herself. But, despite this feeling, she ends by saying: "It is possible that I can go out and find my freedom and be in a safe place." (empirical material from earlier research, Cetrez & DeMarinis, 2017)

4.2.2.2. Extreme responses

Extreme responses are most prominent in the absence of a support system or an even bigger lack in access to resources of housing, job, education and healthcare. The prevalent extreme responses have been the feelings of depression, hopelessness, PTSD, alienation, isolation, fear, extreme crying and regrettably suicide and suicide attempts. These responses denote the importance of migrants having something to attribute meaning to (material or immaterial). When these are unavailable, there is a tendency towards extreme responses.

Linking back to the adaptive responses, cultural values and practices are not only protective, but some individuals, not least youth and women, find themselves oppressed by certain cultural practices or feel entrapped within a series of cultural standards they are not able to live up to. As cultural components, both family and community are at once important sources of social support and at the same time sources of social pressure. An important aspect here is the vacuum that may arise, when individuals try to free themselves from earlier oppressing structures and are encouraged to free themselves, but are not able to, or not given space to find a new functioning structure. This condition of disillusionment or lack of functioning meaning-making system results in weaker self-esteem, indicating a lower ability for evaluating one's sense of self-worth and self-competence. Self-competence is closely linked to agency, a sense of being confident, capable and efficacious.

5. Conclusions

A conceptual problem with much of the research on health among migrants is the focus on the post-migration context, at the expense of the pre-migration context, as well as the transition phase. This implies, in a hidden way, that the “post” is a place of order, safety, justice, resourcefulness, health, democratic. Post-migration is considered the norm of what is right, even universal, since it is linked to “our” context and “our” identity. In parallel, this is differentiated to the “pre”, the refugee’s place of origin, as the opposite, chaotic, unorganised, dangerous, unjust, lacking resources, unhealthy, undemocratic or simply much of that which is connoted to the “other”. More than that, the “other” is a part that needs to be understood, categorised and educated, in order to be disciplined and normalised so it fits into the normative system of the receiving society.

The social anthropologist Alessandro Monsutti pointed out that migration can no longer be seen as a “mere passage from one location to another, but instead as a complex phenomenon characterised by recurrent and multidirectional movements during which a variety of links are woven” (2010, 61). By highlighting mobility as a strategy and part of human development and life cycle, we are able to recognise the agency of migrants or refugees, as seen in this report. To challenge the traditional understanding of refugees as leaving one place for another, or as passive actors who only submit to policies and whose return is highly uncertain, we first need a new subject position for refugees, as people who try to find constructive solutions to life threatening situations and as people who generate new forms of knowledge and information. As Monsutti (2010) writes, the refugee is a mobile and strategic actor, who responds to difficulties, makes use of social and cultural resources to survive and adapt.

Migrants are mobile in the sense that they cross and negotiate between cultural borders, they make use of the resources available, they adopt and they transfer knowledge and cultural values. But, let us not beautify migration. For migrants, there are far too many boundaries to be negotiated - the long-drawn out refugee condition, as well as the legal, political, socio-economic, cultural, religious differences, all linked to old and new societies and many with distinctly negative valency - than any receiving society can accommodate. Some content from the past may never be integrated into the new life conditions in a comfortable way, but will most probably remain as a disturbing memory, as a rejection and exclusion that resists symbolisation and acts on the person in unconscious, compulsive and possibly destructive ways. It is here the memories of the past become an obstacle for the present and future, expressed through PTSD.

Second, instead of a pre-and-post focus, we need to shift the perspective to a transitional position for those involved, simply because the refugee never lives in a post-situation alone, as he/she continuously looks back to what is left in the place of origin, as well as to friends and family left behind. Using inspiration from the Dutch-born clinical psychologist W. Pruyser (1916-1987), who derived his concepts from object-relation theory and the child psychologist D. W. Winnicott’s definition of “transitional experience”, or “transitional space”, a refugee is a person who finds her/himself in a situation where subject/object perspectives interpenetrate and the subject/object positions are temporarily suspended. Instead of viewing the human growth as a move from pre- to post-migration, or give up the old and give in to the new, we may, in line with Pruyser (1974), view human development as the interplay between these two dimensions, an intermediary position that generates new cultural expressions, new stories and new forms of imagining, or what

Pruyser termed as the “illusionistic world.” Being able to communicate these new cultural expressions is important for healthy psychosocial development, so the individual can negotiate between her/his inner psychological processes and outer interpersonal relations (DeMarinis, in Geels & Wikström, 2017), so that social determinants, obstacles and challenges, become a source of development and resilience. But, for this to take place, a welcoming and open reception context is necessary.

6. Policy recommendations:

- Program administrators and policymakers, when responding to resilience-based initiatives, should develop their initiatives in the social-ecological context of family and community resilience. In other words, resilience initiatives should be based on modifying existing resilience processes.
- In program development, attention needs to be paid to different levels and types of resilience, such as both recovery from trauma, as well as sustainability, learning and gaining from the experience.
- Policies and programs that support community and social healing processes can be powerful and cost-effective tools, especially among cultures with more collectivistic beliefs.
- Enhance the competence in cultural meaning making systems among practitioners and interpreters.
- Pay attention to gender and age specific health concerns in integration policies and health programmes.
- Provide individuals with specialized medical assistance and coping resources that are culturally sensitive and linguistically adjusted.
- Distribute information among newcomers about their rights for healthcare and how to access the healthcare services in their own language.
- Establish anti-discrimination policies in the healthcare context.
- Provide psychological treatment where such treatment is lacking, as many refugees suffer from mental health diseases.
- Conduct screening of mental health condition among refugees

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